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Master Thesis Bioinformatics

Prediction of genes in genomes with ambiguous genetic codes

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Abstract

Ciliates of the class *Karyorelictea* use a non-standard genetic code, where the two standard stop-codons UAA and UAG have been repurposed to always code for the amino-acid glutamine, and the standard stop-codon UGA has two functions: It can either code for tryptophan (termed *sense-UGA*), or terminate translation (termed *stop-UGA*). While the code itself hence is ambiguous, the individual UGA-codon is not ambiguous, but efficiently recognized by the cell as either sense-UGA or stop-UGA, with little error.^[19]

Conventional gene-predictors do not accommodate this code-ambiguity. Thus, gene-prediction was to be adapted to karyorelicts (*Loxodes magnus* in particular) to handle this nonstandard code, aiming for better predictions. The conventional predictor used as a reference and target of this endeavour was AUGUSTUS, which uses a generalized hidden Markov model (GHMM) to make *ab initio* gene predictions^[17].

The difference between sense- and stop-UGA was characterized using protein homology information to infer the position of the stop in transcriptome-sequences, reproducing a depletion of UGA (and UAA) before stop- but not sense-UGA that was previously suggested to be the result of the mechanism used by the cell to tell the two apart: UGA-codons would probably be ambiguous even to the cell, if they occurred in this region. To avoid the unfavourable random termination that such a UGA-codon would cause, UGA is fully depleted from a short coding segment right upstream of the proper stop^[19].

As expected, directly running AUGUSTUS on a set of manually annotated genes did not yield convincing prediction results, neither in terms of numerical quality-measures, nor upon visual inspection. A simplistic ‘cleaning’ approach was tried out to improve the prediction results: The sequences were preprocessed to replace sense-UGA by UGG (equally coding for tryptophan) using a very simple probabilistic model to tell sense- from stop-UGA and UGA outside coding sequences. This did not clearly improve the prediction, with both standard AUGUSTUS and AUGUSTUS after preprocessing failing to predict even a single intron entirely correctly. As introns are important for predicting the correct reading frame, a more complicated prediction/preprocessing-approach was deemed necessary: Following the mathematical framework used by AUGUSTUS, a custom GHMM for full gene prediction was designed, implemented and trained on the manual annotation data, yielding mostly better predictions: The majority of introns and exons were correctly predicted, with better sensitivity and precision than any AUGUSTUS-variant tested.

Zusammenfassung

Wimpertierchen der Klasse *Karyorelictea* weichen in ihrem genetischen Code vom „universellen“ Code dergestalt ab, dass die üblichen Stop-Codons UAA und UAG stets in Glutamin übersetzt werden, während das dritte Standardstopcodon UGA entweder in Tryptophan übersetzt wird („sense-UGA“) oder die Translation beendet („stop-UGA“). Dadurch ist zwar der Code uneindeutig, allerdings ist das einzelne UGA-Codon in seiner Funktion für die Zelle eindeutig jeweils nur „sense-UGA“ oder „stop-UGA“.

Übliche Genvorhersageprogramme sind außer Stande, unmittelbar mit einem solchen Code umzugehen. Daher war, ausgehend vom bestehenden Genvorhersageprogramm AUGUSTUS^[17], eine Lösung neu zu entwickeln, um die Genvorhersagequalität auf ein annehmbares Niveau zu bringen.

Zunächst wurde der Unterschied zwischen „sense-UGA“ und „stop-UGA“ anhand des Transkripts von *Loxodes magnus* genauer erforscht: Protein-homologe aus verwandten Spezies dienten dazu, das eigentliche Stop-Codon auffindig zu machen, so dass alle anderen UGAs im Leseraster als „sense-UGA“ erkannt werden konnten. Übereinstimmend mit vorausgehender Literatur^[19] konnte gezeigt werden, dass „sense-UGA“ in einem kurzen Sequenzabschnitt direkt vor dem „stop-UGA“ nicht vorkommt (und weiter UAA dort sehr selten ist). Dies ist vermutlich darauf zurückzuführen, dass UGA in diesem Abschnitt auch der Zelle uneindeutig wäre, und zu nachteiligem, vorzeitigem Translationsabbruch führen würde, weshalb die Selektion dazu führt, dass UGA aus diesem Bereich entfernt wird.^[19]

Ein Satz Übungsdaten wurde händisch annotiert, und zusätzlich für die letztendliche Leistungsmessung noch um einen Satz Testdaten ergänzt. Wie erwartet erbrachte AUGUSTUS keine guten Vorhersagen. Auch ein einfacher Vorverarbeitungsschritt, bei dem „sense-UGA“ anhand eines banalen probabilistischen Modells erkannt werden, und dann durch UGG (codiert ebenfalls Tryptophan) ersetzt werden sollte, lieferte keine eindeutig bzw. überzeugend besseren Ergebnisse. Insbesondere konnte keine der ausprobierten AUGUSTUS-Varianten auch nur ein einziges Intron gänzlich korrekt erkennen. Da Introns dafür, das Leseraster richtig zu erkennen, wichtig sind, und ein Vorverarbeitungsschritt, der Introns miteinbezieht bereits (teilweise) Gene vorhersagt, wurde nach Vorbild AUGUSTUSens ein generalisiertes verdecktes Markowmodell (GHMM) neu speziell für die Genvorhersage in *Karyorelictea* entwickelt. Dieses Modell war denn auch geeignet, glaubwürdig Gene vorherzusagen, und erkannte im Test insbesondere jeweils die Mehrheit der Exons und Introns richtig (bemessen durch Empfindlichkeit und Genauigkeit, die diesbezüglich über den Werten aller AUGUSTUS-Varianten lagen).

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List of Abbreviations

karyorelict	species in the class <i>Karyorelictea</i>
BLAST	basic local alignment search tool
BLASTX	BLAST of translated nucleotide sequence against a protein sequence database
BLASTN	BLAST of nucleotide sequence against a nucleotide sequence database
GHMM	generalised hidden Markov model
MIC	micronucleus
MAC	macronucleus
Σ^*	Kleene star operator applied to countable set Σ
Σ^+	Kleene plus operator applied to countable set Σ
\emptyset	average, mean
Q_2	median
PPM	position probability matrix
PWM	position weight matrix
KL	Kullback-Leibler divergence
%GC	GC-content
NCS	Non-coding sequence/segment
CDS	Coding DNA segment
nt	nucleotides, as a length-measure along a nucleotide-sequence
aa	amino-acids, as a length-measure along a nucleotide- or protein-sequence
$[a : b] := [a, b] \cap \mathbb{Z}$	Interval-like notation for integers (analogously for open intervals), avoided where sensible
$\sum_i a_{i_} := (\sum_i (a_i))$	Notational shortcut to make it clear what is being summed up, and what is not (to avoid ambiguity)

The usual IUPAC one-letter codes are used for amino-acids and nucleobases.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Biological background

1.1.1 Ciliates use a range of non-standard genetic codes

In the time since the proposal of the ‘universal’ genetic code, it has been found that a number of variants of this code indeed exist, e.g. in mitochondria. Ciliates, the members of the protist phylum *Ciliophora*^[7], show a particularly diverse range of alternate genetic codes, with stop-codons being repurposed to translate into amino-acids. These code variants occur in no trivial pattern along the ciliate phylogenetic tree, with distantly related species like *Tetrahymena thermophila* and *Oxytricha trifallax* sharing the same code, while *Euplotes crassus*, which is more closely related to *Tetrahymena*, uses a different code. In another extreme example, the ciliate class *Heterotrichea* includes *Stentor coeruleus*, which uses the standard genetic code, *Condylostoma magnum*, which uses a genetic code in which all three stop codons ambiguously code for either an amino-acid or translation termination, and *Blepharisma japonicum*, which has an unambiguous genetic code, where UGA has been repurposed to always code for tryptophan.^[19]

Furthermore, ciliates have two types of nuclei (nuclear dimorphism): The somatic, usually polyploid macronucleus is the site of transcription, determining the cell’s phenotype, while the germline micronuclei hold the DNA passed on to sexual progeny, but are transcriptionally quiet. In many ciliates, once formed by rearranging and removing certain parts of the micronuclear genome, and then amplifying it, the macronucleus can divide in asexual reproduction as an alternative to sexual reproduction.^[14] Since the genome of the micronucleus is usually edited when differentiating into a macronucleus, there is a genetic difference between the two, in the presence of so called internal eliminated segments (IES) in the micronuclear genome,

which may interrupt genes and thus have to be excised reliably and precisely^[22].

Here, the two karyorelict species *Loxodes magnus* and *Loxodes striatus* (mainly the earlier) were studied, and the heterotrich *Blepharisma japonicum*, as well as some other ciliates, were considered for reference.

1.1.2 Karyorelict ciliates have an ambiguous genetic code

Ciliates of the class^[7] *Karyorelictea* have repurposed all three stop-codons of the standard genetic code (those being: UGA, UAA and UAG^[4]) to code for amino-acids: UAA and UAG both code for glutamine, while UGA can either code for tryptophan, or be a stop. Other than that, their genetic code is the same as the standard^{[4],[19]}.

The behaviour of UGA then is of key interest for gene prediction: a specific UGA-codon is not ambiguous to the cell, but instead is either efficiently translated, or efficiently causes translation termination^[19]. These two states of UGA are here called sense-UGA, which is (almost) always translated into tryptophan, and stop-UGA, which (nearly) always terminates translation. Whether a given UGA is sense or stop is not trivially visible from the genetic sequence, making gene prediction more difficult.

1.1.3 *Loxodes magnus*

The organism worked on in this thesis was *Loxodes magnus*, a karyorelict ciliate commonly found in eutrophic standing freshwater all around the world. Mainly inhabiting the benthos, it can also survive as part of the plankton. It feeds on algae, and is light-sensitive, preferring lower light-levels, and dying off at too strong illumination.^[9] At a body-length of about 0.3 – 0.6mm, it is a fairly large microorganism, with an oblong, somewhat flattened body and a clearly marked mouth. One side of the body is fully covered in cilia, and this side is used to move on a solid substrate (akin to a snail's foot).^[6]

L. magnus has two *paradiploid* macronuclei^[15], which results in a smaller proportion of the overall DNA in the cell being found in the macronucleus compared to the situation in other, typically polyploid ciliates.^[14] That is, the DNA-content of each macronucleus is only slightly higher than that of the single diploid micronucleus of *L. magnus* – and since the genome is nontrivially edited and amplified when a macronucleus is formed, this does not exactly correspond to the notion of diploidy in more familiar eukaryotes.^[15] Further, the macronuclei of *L. magnus* (and all other karyorelict species)

do not divide for asexual reproduction, instead, they are distributed among the daughter cells, and one copy of the micronucleus differentiates into a macronucleus in either daughter-cell.^[15]

1.2 Gene prediction with generalized hidden Markov models

Since the 1990s, generalized hidden Markov models have been successfully used for gene prediction in eukaryotes, as implemented e.g. in Genie^[11]. In eukaryotes, genes are suborganized into introns and exons, where the introns are removed from the pre-mRNA before translation, and thus for gene-prediction have to be precisely detected as a prerequisite to correctly inferring the reading frame of the exons, which poses a challenge for gene-prediction when compared to prokaryotes.

One widely used gene-prediction tool is called AUGUSTUS, initially developed by Mario Stanke^[17], and still maintained by him and affiliates – this is the tool that served as a reference and starting point to the present thesis. The theoretical basis of AUGUSTUS, and some details about its prediction-model will be given here, as relevant for the present work.

Since the problem of gene prediction operates on nucleotide sequences, which are discrete both in the possible positions along their length, and in the ‘values’ (bases) at any particular position, the discussion will be entirely limited to discrete series of discrete random variables.

1.2.1 Generalized hidden Markov models

As indicated by the name, generalized hidden Markov models are hidden Markov models, which again are Markov chains. A Markov chain of order $k \geq 1$ is a sequence of random variables $X_1, X_2, \dots \in Q$, with Q being a countable set of observable states, where the distribution of these random variables fulfills:

$$P([X_i = x_i] | [X_{i-1} = x_{i-1}, \dots, X_1 = x_1]) = P([X_i = x_i] | [X_{i-1} = x_{i-1}, \dots, X_{i-k} = x_{i-k}])$$

for all $i > k$ and all possible realizations $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i \in Q$. That is, not the entire state-history x_1, \dots, x_i has a bearing on the probability of the next state, but only the previous k states. The event $X_i = q \in Q$ is read as the chain being *in state q at time i* .

If this probability does not depend on i (i.e. does not change over time), the Markov chain is called *homogeneous*, otherwise, it is called *inhomogeneous*.^[17]

Often, homogeneous Markov chains of order 1 are used, in which case the next state depends only on the current state. Thus, the transition probabilities $P([X_i = x_i][X_{i-1} = x_{i-1}])$ form the entries of the so-called transition matrix B ^[17]:

$$b_{r,s} = P([X_i = s][X_{i-1} = r]), \quad r, s \in Q$$

This transition matrix can then be understood, and visualized, as the adjacency matrix of a weighted and directed graph, whose nodes are the states Q .

For notational simplicity, Stanke introduces an initial state q_{init} and a terminal state q_{term} , with the model always starting in the initial state, i.e. $X_0 := q_{init}$ is added before the sequence X_1, X_2, \dots , and the probability of leaving the terminal state, once it has been reached, being zero. That is, the transition matrix A over the modified set of states $Q' = Q \cup \{q_{init}, q_{term}\}$ is demanded to fulfill^[17]:

- $\forall q \in Q' : a_{q,q_{init}} = 0$, i.e. the initial state is immediately left, and never taken again
- $a_{q_{init},q_{term}} = 0$, at least one actual state $q \in Q$ has to be taken, the chain cannot end immediately
- $\exists q \in Q : a_{q,q_{term}} > 0$, the terminal state can be reached from some state
- $P([\inf\{t | X_t = q_{term}\} < \infty]) = 1$: the Markov chain almost surely reaches the terminal state
- $a_{q_{term},q_{term}} = 1$, the terminal state is never left

In such a Markov chain, our observations are directly the states taken over time, i.e. we would observe a certain sequence x_1, x_2, \dots, x_T of states, and then the Markov chain allows us to assign a probability to this sequence. For gene prediction however, we would want the model's states to capture sequence-types like coding sequence versus intron, which is information we cannot directly observe in the sequence – and hence need to make some prediction. In other words, we introduce a split between the *emitted observations* Y_i , and the *hidden states* X_i whenceforth these emissions came. While the hidden states still take values in Q' , the observations operate on the so-called *emission alphabet* Σ (a countable set, here: $\Sigma = \{T, G, A, C\}$).^[17]

If all the model's states emit only single symbols $u \in \Sigma$, the resulting model is called a *hidden Markov model* (HMM). If however, to introduce some modularity into the model by allowing each state to basically function as a

submodel, the states are allowed to emit nonempty words $\sigma \in \Sigma^+$, the model is a *generalized hidden Markov model* (GHMM).^[17]

In mathematical terms, a generalized hidden Markov model with states Q' , emission alphabet Σ , transition matrix A , and emission probabilities $e_{i,j,\tau}(\sigma)$ is a series $(X_0, Y_0), (X_1, Y_1), \dots$ of pairs of random variables, where X_0, X_1, \dots is a homogeneous Markov chain of order 1 with states Q' , as defined above (with $P([X_0 = q_{init}]) = 1$), and where Y_i is the emission from state x_i at time i . The Y_i take values in Σ^* , as determined by the emission probabilities $e_{x_{i-1}, x_i, \tau}(y_i)$ ($i > 0, x_{i-1}, x_i \in Q', \tau \in \Sigma^*$)^[17]:

$$e_{x_{i-1}, x_i, \tau}(y_i) = P([Y_i = y_i] | [X_i = x_i, X_{i-1} = x_{i-1}, Y_0 Y_1 \dots Y_{i-1} = \tau])$$

Clearly, the dependence of the emission probability on the previous state x_{i-1} , and in particular its dependence on the entire emission-history τ (which is the concatenation of the previous emissions y_0, y_1, \dots, y_{i-1}) introduce a limited capacity for memory into this model, beyond what the Markov-chain X_0, X_1, \dots would enable. While the Y_i can in general take all values in Σ^* , the following two constraints on the emission of the empty word ε are introduced:

- $\forall s \in Q, r \in Q', \tau \in \Sigma^* : e_{r,s,\tau}(\varepsilon) = 0$, no state $s \in Q$ can emit the empty word
- $e_{r,q_{init},\tau}(\varepsilon) = e_{r,q_{term},\tau}(\varepsilon) = 1$, both the initial and the terminal state always emit the empty word^[17]

Stanke introduces these emission probabilities as being parametrized by the previous state and the entire emission history, in addition to the current state and the current emission. Since I never make use of the model's capability for memory, the emission probabilities could as well be defined as:

$$e_{x_i}(y_i) = P([Y_i = y_i] | [X_i = x_i]), \text{ for } x_i \in Q', y_i \in \Sigma^*$$

and indeed, for clarity and brevity, the emission probabilities of the GHMM developed here will be given in the latter form.

1.2.2 Viterbi algorithm

Having a GHMM, one could of course start the model in the initial state, and have it randomly transition from state to state, emitting random sequences – however, here, producing the sequences is of no interest. Instead, the reverse problem is of greater interest: Given a sequence, what is the sequence of states and emission-lengths that best explain the observed sequence (have maximum *a posteriori* probability: MAP-estimate).

Such a sequence is formalized as a *parse*, which is a vector $\phi = ((x_1, d_1), \dots, (x_n, d_n))$ of pairs of states $x_i \in Q$ and emission-lengths $d_i \in \mathbb{N}$. ϕ is said to have n steps and be of length $d_1 + \dots + d_n$.^[17]

Let $(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) = ((X_0, Y_0), (X_1, Y_1), \dots)$ be a GHMM, then the parse *induced* by (\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) is defined as

$$\phi(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) := ((X_1, |Y_1|), \dots, (X_T, |Y_T|))$$

with X_T being the last state taken before the model entered the terminal state, i.e. $T + 1 = \inf\{i | X_i = q_{term}\}$.^[17]

Let $l \in \mathbb{N}$, and let $r := \max\{n : |y_1 \dots y_n| \leq l \wedge x_n \neq q_{term}\}$, then the *l-truncated* parse $\phi_l(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y})$ is defined as

$$\phi_l(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) := ((X_1, |Y_1|), \dots, (X_r, |Y_r|))$$

i.e. the parse up to l , unless l cannot be reached exactly.

Further, the concatenated emitted sequence $Y_0 Y_1 Y_2 \dots$ is denoted by $\sigma(\mathbf{Y})$.^[17]

Deviating slightly from Stanke's notation and in line with the practice in many programming languages (importantly: Java and Python), strings will here be indexed from 0: $\sigma[0, l] := \sigma_0 \sigma_1 \dots \sigma_{l-1}$ (and $\sigma[0, 0] := \varepsilon$).

With these prerequisites, the problem becomes to split the observed sequence $\sigma \in \Sigma^t$ in such pieces of lengths d_i , and find such states x_i , that the parse $((x_i, d_i))_{i=1 \dots n}$ is a MAP-parse. Such a MAP-parse is called a *Viterbi parse* $\psi_{viterbi}$, and can be found with the Viterbi-algorithm (algorithm 1). More formally, a Viterbi-parse fulfills:

$$\psi_{viterbi} \in \underset{\psi \text{ is a parse of length } t}{\operatorname{argmax}} P([\phi(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) = \psi] | [\sigma(\mathbf{Y}) = \sigma])$$

i.e. it maximizes the posterior probability, given the observation σ . To find such a parse, the Viterbi-algorithm makes use of the *Viterbi variables* $\gamma_{q,l}$, which are defined as:

$$\gamma_{q,l} = \max_{\text{parse } \psi \text{ of length } l, \text{ ending in } q} P([\phi_l(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) = \psi] | [\sigma(\mathbf{Y})[0, l] = \sigma[0, l]])$$

for $q \in Q, 1 \leq l \leq t$. Setting $\gamma_{q_{init}, 0} = 1$ and $\forall q \neq q_{init} : \gamma_{q, 0} = 0$, it can be shown^[17], that this can be reformulated as the following recursive formula:

$$\gamma_{q,l} = \max_{(q', l') \in Q \times [1:l] \cup \{(q_{init}, 0)\}} \gamma_{q', l'} \cdot a_{q', q} \cdot e_{q', q, \sigma[0, l']} (\sigma[l', l]) \quad (1.1)$$

Note that these $\gamma_{q,l}$ form a $|Q| \times t$ -matrix, where the computation of every cell requires a maximization over all columns to the left of it (maximization over $[1 : l')$), leading to a quadratic runtime in the length t of the sequence σ .

Algorithm 1: Viterbi Algorithm**Input:** sequence $\sigma \in \Sigma^+$ **Output:** Viterbi-parse $\psi = ((q_n, l_n - l_{n+1}), \dots, (q_1, l_1 - l_2))$ **1: Computing the Viterbi-variables****for** $q \in Q \cup \{q_{term}\}$ **do** initialize the table| $\gamma_{q,0} = 0$ **end** $\gamma_{q_{init},0} = 1$ **for** $l = 1, \dots, t$ **do**| **for** $q \in Q$ **do**

| | Find the maximum as specified in equation 1.1:

| | $\gamma_{q,l} \leftarrow \gamma_{q_{init},0} \cdot a_{q_{init},q} \cdot e_{q_{init},q,\varepsilon}(\sigma[0,l])$ | | **for** $q' \in Q$ **do**| | | **for** $l' = 0, \dots, l - 1$ **do**| | | | $\gamma_{q,l} \leftarrow \max\{\gamma_{q,l}, \gamma_{q',l'} \cdot a_{q',q} \cdot e_{q',q,\sigma[0,l']}(\sigma[l',l])\}$ | | | **end**| | **end**| **end****end****2: Traceback to find the MAP-parse** $(q_1, l_1) \leftarrow (\operatorname{argmax}_{q \in Q} \{\gamma_{q,t} \cdot a_{q,q_{term}}\}, t)$ $i \leftarrow 2$ **while** $l_{i-1} > 0$ **do**| $(q_i, l_i) \leftarrow \operatorname{argmax}_{(q,l) \in Q \times \{1:l_{i-1}\} \cup \{(q_{init},0)\}} \gamma_{q,l} \cdot a_{q,q_{i-1}} \cdot e_{q,q_{i-1},\sigma[0,l]}(\sigma[l, l_{i-1}])$ | $i \leftarrow i + 1$ **end** $n \leftarrow i - 2$

1.2.3 Augustus

The model employed by AUGUSTUS will here be outlined, so as to make it clear where the GHMM developed in this thesis differs from it. Details of the AUGUSTUS-model which are not particularly important to this thesis will generally be omitted, and can be read up in the original publication^[17].

The model fundamentally is organized in two chiral subparts, one for genes on the forward strand, and one for genes on the reverse strand. As a consequence of this separation, genes on opposing strands, that overlap, cannot be discerned by this model. Genes are then modelled as being either single-exon genes, or containing introns, with this difference manifesting as

two separate groups of states modelling single-exon genes (one state), and any other gene (22 states) respectively. Fifteen of these 22 latter states are dedicated entirely to modelling introns. Since an intron can introduce three kinds of frame-shifts (no shift, shift by one nucleotide, shift by two nucleotides), which have to be kept separate in the model and in prediction, these fifteen intron-states again are three groups of five states each, with each of these three groups instantiating the same intron-model. Thus, the actual intron-model has only five states, as shown in figure 1.1 B:

An intron starts with a splice-donor-site (SDS) of a few conserved nucleotides around where the intron is spliced out, and ends with a similarly conserved splice-acceptor-site (SAS). The SAS is further preceded by a sequence containing the branch-point for forming the lariat, which is modelled jointly with the SAS in a common state. Both of these intron-edges are of a fixed length. The variability of intron-lengths thus must be captured by the remaining three states.

Empirically, in many species, intron lengths are distributed around a fairly short (under 100nt^[17]) mode, but very long introns are observed too, following roughly a geometric distribution. To accommodate this, AUGUSTUS differentiates between two kinds of introns: short introns have a fairly narrow length distribution fit to the training-dataset, whereas long introns have a minimum length and a geometrically distributed excess length therebeyond. The length distribution of short introns is then naturally captured by the emission-length distribution from the corresponding state I_{short} , while the geometric length distribution is implemented by a state I_{geo} which only emits single nucleotides and allows transitions to itself.

A gene always starts with a start-codon that follows a conserved translation-initiation-motif and is followed by a highly conserved initial pattern (together, these are part of the so-called Kozak-consensus-sequence around the start-AUG^[24]). AUGUSTUS further allows the initial part of a gene ('initial content model' in figure 1.1 A) to differ in composition from the composition generally observed in exons ('exon content model' in figure 1.1 A). Noteworthy, no such distinction is made for the region preceding the stop-codon that ends every gene. The exon-states (which will not be discussed in more detail here) make use of more submodels (of no particular interest here) to capture the empirical exon-length distribution, and the different composition of these exon-parts.^[17]

Both the very narrow, non-geometric intron length distribution found in *Loxodes magnus* and other ciliates^[3], and AUGUSTUS requiring a deterministic stop-codon, render AUGUSTUS unfit to directly predict genes in

karyorelicts.

Figure 1.1: Parts of the GHMM used by AUGUSTUS: **A** gene-model as implemented by the GHMM (figure unmodified from^[17]): The upper part shows a gene with three exons and two introns (one long and one short), the lower part shows a single-exon gene. Note that Stanke refers to splice-donor- and splice-acceptor-sites as ‘dss’ and ‘ass’ respectively^[17]. **B** intron-model (adapted from^[17]): The upper path (via I_{short}) models short introns (as exemplified in **A**), while the lower path (via I_{geo}) models long introns as having a *geometrical* length distribution.

1.3 Aim and structure

The aim of this master project was to predict genes in karyorelict species, *Loxodes magnus* in particular, with better performance than the existing gene prediction software AUGUSTUS can muster. To this end, gene prediction approaches as designed to fit various eukaryotes, were to be adapted and specialized for the particular case presented by karyorelict species.

The project is structured in four parts:

1. Characterizing the difference between stop- and sense-UGA from RNA-sequences and homology-information
2. Manually annotating a set of genes to be used for training and testing gene prediction software
3. Assessing the performance of AUGUSTUS, when trained on this data, and characterizing problems of its predictions, potentially finding simple 'hacks' to improve the predictions
4. Adapt gene prediction to the karyorelict code

Chapter 2

Materials and Methods

2.1 Datasets

I did not acquire any new experimental data for this thesis, and did not perform the quality-control and assembly steps to generate the used datasets, instead relying on the data acquired by the Swart-Lab, and online databases. Due to the Corona-crisis, some data-acquisition in the Lab was delayed.

Two main datasets of *Loxodes magnus* macronuclear genetic information were used: a transcriptome-assembly (RNA), and a draft genome assembly (DNA). The reads for both were generated with Illumina sequencing. The DNA-reads were assembled using SPAdes^[2], and cleaned of micronuclear and mitochondrial, as well as algal and bacterial contamination. Of the RNA-reads, those mapping to the macronuclear draft genome assembly were assembled into the transcriptome using TRINITY^[10]. Since RNA-sequencing was directional, the assembled transcriptome should largely be on the forward strand.

Furthermore, a read-mapping of the RNA reads to the macronuclear draft genome was provided in sorted bam-format^[13], generated with Hisat2^[12].

A ciliate protein database was readily provided, containing protein sequences of *Euplotes vannus*, *Oxytricha trifallax*, *Stentor coeruleus*, *Tetrahymena borealis*, *T. elioti*, *T. malaccensis*, and *T. thermophila*, retrieved from the ciliates.org databases^[18].

2.2 Characterizing the difference between sense- and stop-UGA

2.2.1 Homology-based heuristic for finding stop-UGA

To identify a first set of stop-UGAs, a homology-based heuristic previously employed to the same end^[19], [Supplementary materials](#), was adopted:

From the transcriptome assembly, such contigs ending in at least seven consecutive adenines were deemed ‘poly-A-tailed’. These poly-A-tailed transcripts were compared to the reference database of ciliate proteins by BLASTx, using the karyorelict nuclear code (NCBI genetic code 27^[4]) for translation of the query sequences and an e-value cutoff of 10^{-6} . Thereby, each transcript is assigned a number of hits (maybe zero), which may cover different parts of the query sequence, and, since the reference were protein sequences, indicate the reading-frame. The first in-frame UGA downstream of the hit ending to closest to the 3'-end of the transcript was searched, and, if found, deemed the stop-UGA. Further, the number of the top-ten hits (with respect to alignment-score) which ended within six amino-acids from the putative stop-UGA was assessed as a heuristic to exclude spurious hits. The subsequent analysis was restricted to those transcripts, where a certain minimum number of the top-ten hits fulfilled this criterion. The exact threshold was varied between different analyses, to balance the inclusion of uninformative transcripts (undesired, increases with lower threshold) with sample-size (desired, increases with lower threshold).

2.2.2 Querying simple sequence properties based on the found stop

Using the putative stops as identified by the above heuristic, a number of sequence properties were assessed:

3' UTR lengths: in those transcripts, where all the top ten hits were within six amino-acids from the putative stop, 3' UTR lengths were measured as the number of nucleotides between the stop-UGA's A and the 5'-end of the poly-A-tail. This was done mainly to assess the reliability of the heuristic by checking whether it reproduces the narrow UTR-length-distribution and overall short UTRs found in other ciliates^[19], and to guide manual annotation later.

Base frequencies in CDS versus 3' UTR: The frequency with which each base occurs at a given position relative to the inferred stop-codon was collected, in a window from 72nt upstream to 30nt downstream of the stop-UGA's U. It was expected that the GC-content would be higher in the coding

sequence upstream of the stop, and lower downstream, as previously found in other karyorelicts^[19].

Codon usage in the region before the stop-UGA: It had been previously found in karyorelicts, that the UGA-codon is depleted in a small window (about 20nt) upstream of the stop-UGA^[19]. To reproduce this result and investigate it further, the in-frame occurrences of codons around the putative stop were counted for each codon position, within a range of 70 codons upstream to 20 codons downstream of the stop, yielding a codon distribution for each of these positions. Further, an empirical codon usage in the CDS upstream of this special region, and within this region was retrieved. This was also compared with the situation around the other standard-stop-codons (UAA and UAG), as well as the codon usage around sense-UGA.

Further, the quality of the used heuristic, and the informativeness of the findings was directly assessed by comparing results across ciliate species:

Codon usage in the region before the stop in other ciliates: To check whether any of the codon preferences found in the upstream proximity of the stop in *Loxodes magnus* are a feature particular to *Loxodes* and related to the ambiguity of its genetic code, the codon usage in the same region was assessed in two ciliates with unambiguous codes for which a sufficient annotation was available: *Stentor coeruleus*, which uses the standard code, and *Tetrahymena thermophila*, which uses only UGA as a stop (unambiguously), while the other two stop-codons code for Glutamine. For *Stentor* of course, none of the stop-codons are expected to ever be used upstream of the stop (or only very few read-through stop-codons, which can occur in species using the standard code^[19]), while *Tetrahymena* could show a depletion of the repurposed UAA or UAG. If the mechanism of translation-termination based on proximity to the poly-A-tail, as proposed by Swart et al.^[19], or a similar mechanism, indeed underlies the disambiguation of UGA in karyorelicts, there would be little reason for *Tetrahymena* to show some pattern of depletion (as *Tetrahymena*'s code does not need to be disambiguated).

Verifying the heuristic using conserved proteins: A set of highly conserved proteins (core histones and ribosomal proteins) was collected from the annotation of *Tetrahymena* (because the annotation of *Stentor* and other ciliates was worse and/or did not include protein classification/identification), and their amino-acid sequences were retrieved manually using Geneious Prime 2020.1.2^[8] (under the 'ciliate' genetic code^[4]). The *Loxodes* transcriptome assembly was BLASTed against this reference (using the karyorelict genetic code for translation in all reading frames), revealing which transcripts probably code

for these proteins. With these conserved proteins, one can be fairly sure about where they end, and thus about the actual stop-UGA (more so than for the random proteins used in the heuristic). The sequence characteristics (3' UTR length, base usage, UGA-depletion) queried for the larger dataset yielded by the heuristic were also assessed for this more certain dataset, to check for a clear indication that the heuristic is faulty (e.g. frequently finding UGA directly upstream of the stop-UGA).

2.2.3 Searching for sequence motifs: PPMs and PWMs

One possibility how the cell could tell the two states of UGA apart would be the recognition of some sequence motif encoding the state. Previous research suggests that this motif is the poly-A-tail^[19], which is inaccessible from the genomic sequence and thus not of use for calling genes thence. Still, sequence motifs were searched by constructing position probability matrices (PPM) and position weight matrices (PWM) of the sequences around three types of UGA: sense-UGA, stop-UGA and UGA in the 3' UTR. Sense-UGA is flanked on both sides by coding sequence, stop-UGA is preceded by coding and followed by noncoding sequence, and UGA and the 3' UTR is flanked on both sides by noncoding sequence. Thus, besides searching for sequence motifs around UGA, these matrices also capture general properties of coding sequence versus noncoding sequence, which may by itself be useful for gene-prediction.

To construct a position weight matrix, the empirical positional base frequencies $f_{b,i}$ are collected for all bases b at all positions i , where the range of considered positions defines the window wherein a motif is searched^[23]. To deal with cases where a certain base is never seen at a certain position by pure chance due to a insufficient dataset, pseudocounts are used: one occurrence of each base in each position outside the UGA is simply assumed. These frequencies $f_{b,i}$ form a position probability matrix F (also called a position-specific frequency matrix, PSFM^[1]), whose entries are estimates of the probability of seeing base b at position i – importantly however, the PPM does not take any prior knowledge about the base distribution into account. The position-weight-matrix W then is constructed from F by taking such a prior into account:

$$W_{b,i} = \log_2 \frac{f_{b,i}}{p_b} \text{ or } W_{b,i} = \log_2 \frac{f_{b,i}}{p_{b,i}}$$

where p_b or $p_{b,i}$ is the prior (background frequency model) probability of seeing base b (at position i) – which usually is position-independent^[23]. However, since i here already know that the background frequencies will differ between CDS and NCS, a more closely fit prior is chosen: For those positions i which are in coding sequences, the empirical average base frequencies found in

coding sequences are used as a background model, while for those i in the 3' UTR, the empirical NCS base-frequencies are used.

To compare the retrieved matrices, the Kullback-Leibler divergence between a pair of probability matrices F, G is computed^[1]:

$$\text{KL}(F\|G) = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{i=1}^w \sum_{b \in \{T, C, A, G\}} F_{b,i} \log \frac{F_{b,i}}{G_{b,i}}$$

where w is the length of the motif. Note that the Kullback-Leibler is not symmetric, so it is symmetricized into a distance measure

$$d(F, G) = \frac{\text{KL}(F\|G) + \text{KL}(G\|F)}{2}$$

Aerts *et al.* consider two motifs to be similar when their $d(F, G) < 0.2$, in which case they deem them redundant for their purposes^[1].

2.3 Manual annotation based on homology

Manual annotation was done in Geneious Prime 2020.1.2^[8], on a subset of the data provided: The poly-A-terminated transcripts were nucleotide-BLASTed against the macronuclear draft genome, to find whence they had been transcribed. Then, a `bed`-file was generated specifying to which contigs of the genome-assembly any transcript mapped at all, and on this contig, to which stretch of sequence, as defined by a start and an end index. The start and end were not chosen to be exactly the start and end of the respective blast-hit, but were extended beyond the blast-hit by 300nt (size of the flanking region). `samtools view`^{[16],[13]} was then fed this `bed`-file for its `-L` argument to extract only those reads which mapped to these regions of interest, where the homology-information gained by the heuristic could guide the annotation. This reduced mapping was loaded into Geneious.

Then, the transcripts were worked through in descending order of the score of the best BLASTx-hit (same BLASTx results as used for the heuristic): Those contigs to which the transcript mapped (BLASTn) were inspected for read-coverage in the respective region, and the region and contig where sufficient read-coverage could be found was further inspected. The N- and C-terminal sequences of the translated transcript were manually searched for at the edges of this region of interest (in forward and reverse frames as translated by Geneious under the custom karyorelict code), taking hints from the poly-A-tail (if present in the reads), the direction of any present introns, and the 3'-UTR-length estimate to guess the distance between the C-terminal

sequence and the poly-A-tail or end of coverage. Mostly, the 3'/C-terminal end was first identified, yielding information about the reading-frame, and thence, the gene was annotated moving upstream towards the start-codon. The 5'/N-terminal end was occasionally extended beyond the BLASTx-match, or pruned well into it, to have the annotated genes start in the obligatory start-codon (ATG). The decision to which ATG-codon to extend or prune was based on the plausibility of this deviation from the BLAST-results with respect to GC-content of the in/excluded sequence (extending into low-%GC sequence is implausible), observed read-coverage, and whether the extension could fit into the hit sequences (the BLAST-hits of course do not all start at the reference-sequence's N-terminus).

From the resulting set of annotated genes, some basic statistics e.g. about the number of introns per gene, or the lengths of introns, were collected and used both to inform the design of the gene-predictor and the judgement of the quality of gene-predictions.

2.4 Testing Augustus on the annotation

2.4.1 Augustus-setup and use

AUGUSTUS had already been used by the Swart-Lab for gene prediction in other ciliates, and a small number of modifications had been made to the source code: In particular, the minimum intron length was set to 12 instead of the usual 39 (internal communication). This slightly modified version of AUGUSTUS, including a number of supplementary Perl-scripts, was available to be run in a server of the Max-Planck-Institute.

A new species-profile was set up for *Loxodes magnus* using the AUGUSTUS-Perl-script `new_species.pl`, and the initial annotation-set was (repeatedly) split randomly into a testing dataset (containing 65 genes) and a training dataset (containing the rest of the annotated genes) using the Perl-script `randomSplit.pl`. Augustus was then trained on the training-dataset, and run on the testing-dataset (both using translation table 6^[4]), yielding measures of sensitivity and specificity of the prediction. Note that the 'testing'-dataset was used to optimize the predictions (by choice of hyperparameters and preprocessing), so it is not a full benchmark/testing-dataset.

2.4.2 Simplistic preprocessing: Sense-UGA-cleaning

Since AUGUSTUS cannot natively deal with an ambiguous stop-codon, but only with unambiguously reassigned ones, preprocessing the genome sequences

to replace all sense-UGA with UGG (which likewise codes for tryptophan), and then training and running AUGUSTUS on such a preprocessed dataset was tried, to improve the predictive performance. Of course, to remove sense-UGA, but not stop-UGA, sense-UGA has to be recognized somehow.

A very simplistic approach to discriminate between sense-UGA on one hand, and stop-UGA and noncoding UGA on the other hand, is to make use of the base-content or the codon usage in the coding sequence as opposed to the codon-structure-free base-frequencies found in non-coding sequences: sense-UGA is flanked on both sides by coding sequence, stop-UGA is flanked to the left by coding and to the right by noncoding sequence, and noncoding UGA is flanked entirely by noncoding sequence. This yields three simple probabilistic models, one for every state UGA can be in. Then, the model under which a given UGA and its flanking sequences are most likely is taken to be the correct explanation of the segment, and the UGA is only replaced with UGG, if it is most likely a sense-UGA. This is also done for the reverse strand, by working on the reverse complement, and then leads to changes of UCA to CCA.

Two types of model are used for the coding sequences: base-wise and codon-wise. The base-wise model assumes that all bases are drawn independently from an underlying distribution (with a higher %GC compared to NCS), which is estimated by the empirical base-frequencies in coding sequences. The codon-wise model meanwhile assumes that the sequence is composed from codons which are drawn independently from an underlying codon distribution, which again is estimated by the empirical codon usage. Importantly, under the codon-wise model, sense-UGA is flanked two segments generally without UGA-depletion, while stop-UGA is flanked by a UGA-free segment to the left – which is not represented in the base-wise model.

The changes in predictive performance induced by this preprocessing, using either a base-wise or a codon-wise model, and different (including asymmetric) flanking-region-sizes, were assessed by preprocessing the entire sequence dataset, then splitting the annotated genes into a test and training set, retraining AUGUSTUS on the modified training set, and finally running it as before.

2.5 A custom GHMM for gene prediction in *Loxodes*

Moving beyond an overly simplistic preprocessing approach, a custom GHMM for predicting genes in *Loxodes magnus* (and probably other karyorelict species) was conceived, and implemented in Java. Inferring the parameters of this

GHMM was automated, with this inference implemented in Python.

2.5.1 Overview: A simpler model for a more specific problem

AUGUSTUS aims to be adaptable/applicable to gene prediction in eukaryotes in general^[17]. This is not the aim of my model – which is why it can be, and indeed is, smaller and more specific to the problem at hand. The model’s states and nonzero transitions are graphically represented in Figure 2.1. Overall, the model has two chiral halves, one for the forward and one for the reverse strand, that only differ slightly, and three states (q_{init} , NCS , q_{term}) that are not strand-specific. The states of the forward-model will be referred to by names starting with ‘+’, and the reverse strand states starting with ‘-’. The discussion will generally be limited to the strand-indifferent and forward-frame states, with not immediately obvious features of the reverse-model pointed out.

When discussing geometric distributions, the terms ‘success’ and ‘failure’ will be used as usual for geometric distributions, with no implication of biological/evolutionary/metabolic success or failure.

Figure 2.1: Graph representation of the GHMM developed in this thesis to predict genes in *Loxodes magnus*: Reverse-strand states are graphically marked by horizontal hatching (but textually marked with a prefixed –), while forward-frame, and frameless states are unpatterned. The initial state q_{init} is represented by a solid black bullet (UML process-diagram) and the terminal state q_{term} is represented by a ringed black bullet. States which can lead to multiple other states (‘decision’ states: NCS and CDS) are marked by a diamond outline. Note that while the reverse-strand intron-flanking states (-1L, -2R, -2L, -1R) connect the same way to the reverse intron-states as the respective forward states, their emission probabilities have to account for the fact that they are on the reverse strand (e.g. +1L emits the first base of a codon, while -1L emits the last base)

2.5.2 Basic gene-model

The centre of the graph in Figure 2.1 shows the part of the model that captures single-exon genes: Coming from the preceding NCS, such a gene starts with a start-codon, followed by the rest of the exon, and ends in a TGA-free stop-region ending in the stop-TGA (this stop-region is $21 + 3$ nucleotides long). Note that, unlike is the case for AUGUSTUS, the stop-region differs from the general ‘exon content model’, while there is no ‘initial content model’ as used in AUGUSTUS^[17].

The start-codon is additionally surrounded (mainly preceded) by a highly conserved sequence (the Kozak consensus sequence), which for ciliates had previously been found to include three near-deterministic adenines directly preceding the start-ATG^[24]. Approximating this, the state $+M$ emits a six-nucleotide sequence, starting with three nucleotides that are strongly biased towards Adenine, and ending deterministically with ATG. Since the gene starts in exactly one start codon, $+M$ is always left after one emission.

$+CDS$ emits one codon at a time, and has a high probability of transitioning back to itself. Thereby, it implements a geometric length distribution: once entered, the state emits a codon, then the model transitions to the next state, most probably again $+CDS$, thus extending the exon. The exon ends, when the model transitions from $+CDS$ to another state (stop or intron states), which happens with a small ‘success’-probability $p_{\text{end}}^{\text{exon}}$

$$p_{\text{end}}^{\text{exon}} = 1 - P([X_{i+1} = +CDS] | [X_i = +CDS]) \quad (2.1)$$

To avoid overfitting to the potentially quite small training dataset, and reduce the number of model-parameters, the emission probabilities for the codons are not immediately the empirical codon usage, which captures statistical dependencies between the bases of the codon, but a simplified codon model that assumes statistical independence of the three bases of each codon. For each position $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ in a codon, the respective base c_i is drawn from a categorical distribution over the nucleobases $b \in \{T, C, A, G\}$:

$$e_{+CDS}(c_1 c_2 c_3) = p_{1,c_1}^{\text{exon}} \cdot p_{2,c_2}^{\text{exon}} \cdot p_{3,c_3}^{\text{exon}}$$

Therefore, the emission probabilities for $+CDS$ are captured by a 3×4 matrix $(p_{i,b}^{\text{exon}})_{i,b}$, in twelve parameters (3 of which are redundant, because $n - 1$ parameters suffice to specify an n -way categorical when it is known that they are correctly normalized), instead of the 64 parameters (one of which is redundant) that are needed to specify the empirical codon usage. This model can still capture a preference for some bases in specific codon positions, which had been shown to already be very informative in discerning whether a given sequence was coding or not (internal communication). The reverse strand

–*CDS* simply operates on the reverse complement of the emission, with the same model and parameters.

The stop-region comprises the TGA-free coding sequence right upstream of the stop-TGA, and the stop-TGA itself. The TGA-free region is set to be 7 codons (21nt) long, based on prior literature^[19] and own findings (see results). These seven codons use a base-wise model $p_{i,b}^{\text{stop}}$ similar to the one used for coding sequence, assuming statistical independence of the three codon positions. This alone would however not suffice to make TGA an impossible codon to occur without inappropriately setting $p_{1,T}^{\text{stop}}, p_{2,G}^{\text{stop}}$ or $p_{3,A}^{\text{stop}}$ to zero. Therefore, in addition to the three categorical distributions for the codon positions, a set R of codons deviating from this model is introduced: a codon $\varrho \in R$ is given the probability $q_{\varrho}^{\text{stop}}$ – which should fulfill $q_{\varrho}^{\text{stop}} \neq p_{1,\varrho_1}^{\text{stop}} \cdot p_{2,\varrho_2}^{\text{stop}} \cdot p_{3,\varrho_3}^{\text{stop}}$ (this is not necessary, but if the two are equal, an explicit correction is nonsense). The overall probabilities of all codons $c_1c_2c_3$ still need to sum up to one after such a correction, i.e.:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &\stackrel{!}{=} \sum_{c_1 \in \{T,C,A,G\}} \sum_{c_2 \in \{T,C,A,G\}} \sum_{c_3 \in \{T,C,A,G\}} P_{\text{stop}}([\vec{C} = c_1c_2c_3]) \quad (2.2) \\ &= \sum_{\varrho \in R} q_{\varrho}^{\text{stop}} + \sum_{\vec{c} \in \{T,C,A,G\}^3 \setminus R} \prod_{i=1}^3 p_{i,c_i}^{\text{stop}} \end{aligned}$$

In the most extreme case, R could contain all codons and just assign each of them its empirical frequency – which is besides the point. In practice, correcting four codons (TGA, TAA, and two algorithmically determined codons, as described in the section ‘Inferring the parameters’) sufficed for a good approximation of the empirical codon usage in the TGA-depleted region, putting the number of parameters for the emission-probabilities of $\pm stop$ at $3 \times 4 + 4 \cdot 2 = 20$ (counting each codon correction as two parameters: ‘which codon?’ and ‘how probable?’) compared to the 64 when using the empirical codon frequencies. Again, like $\pm M$, $\pm stop$ are deterministically left after emitting their sequence.

The *NCS*-state has quite a simple behaviour: With a high probability, the model stays in *NCS*, emitting a single base at a time, based on the empirical frequency of the bases in non-coding sequence (empirical categorical distribution), and with a very low probability switches to $+M$, $-stop$ or q_{term} . Thereby, intergenic regions too are modeled as having a geometric length-distribution.

Note that all the states described so far allow emissions of exactly one length (1 for *NCS*, 6 for $\pm M$, 3 for $\pm CDS$ and 24 for $\pm stop$), and only model the variable length of the respective features (intergenic region: *NCS*, exon:

$\pm CDS$) through the transition-probabilities, not through variable emission-lengths, because a geometric length distribution at least approximately fits the observed situation in *Loxodes magnus*.

2.5.3 Dealing with introns

Introns however, clearly deviate from a geometric length distribution, not just in *Loxodes*^[17], requiring a more complicated approach. Additionally, introns can interrupt a coding sequence in three relevantly different ways: An intron can sit neatly between two codons, or interrupt a codon between its first and second base, or between its second and third base. This leads to the three parallel branches for introns leaving and reentering the CDS-states, as depicted in Figure 2.1, to guarantee that the complete concatenated coding sequence has a length divisible by three.

These three cases are referenced in the state-names based on the number of bases of the *interrupted* codon found to the left and right of the intron: $\pm intron\ 0 - 0$ denotes introns that sit between codons, $\pm intron\ 1 - 2$ are such introns where one base of the codon is found to the left, and two to the right – note however, that this single base to the left is the first base of the codon for $+intron\ 1 - 2$, but the (complement of the) last base of the codon for $-intron\ 1 - 2$, and the corresponding rest of the codon is on the other side. The states $\pm intron\ 1 - 2$ are then naturally preceded by the states $\pm 1L$, which emit the single nucleotide to the left (thence the name), and followed by $\pm 2R$, which emit the two nucleotides to the right. Since the interrupted codon is part of the coding sequence, these intron-flanking states ($\pm 1L, \pm 2L, \pm 1R, \pm 2R$) use the same positional categorical model used by $\pm CDS$, but only emit part of a codon. Apart from these flanking codon parts, the introns behave the same in all three cases both with respect to their sequence and to their length distribution:

An intron starts with a 5nt long splice donor site (SDS), whose first two bases are GT, and ends with a 4nt long splice acceptor site (SAS), whose last two bases are AG. The other positions of these sites show clear biases towards certain bases, but are non-deterministic. The remaining middle part of the intron has a very low GC-content of $\approx 10\%$ (compared to the $\approx 23\%$ found in NCS).

As for the intron-lengths, it was observed both in *Loxodes* and other species (like *Drosophila melanogaster*^[17] and ciliates like *Paramecium*^[3]), that the distribution has one very dominant mode, with potentially a number of smaller modes for longer introns^[18], and most introns have a length within a quite narrow range around this mode (see Figure 3.9). In *Paramecium*,^[3]

and *Loxodes*, the intron-length distribution may have just a single mode, with introns beyond a certain length either absent, or very rare. While AUGUSTUS employs a mixed model combining a geometric distribution implemented through state-transitions (as done here for CDS and NCS) with an explicit length distribution implemented by the emission probabilities of an alternative state^[17], here, introns are assumed to have a hard maximum and minimum length. Thus, a number of distributions on a limited range $l \in \{\min, \min + 1, \dots, \max\}$ was tried out, including two variants of the Poisson distribution (which is very convenient for parameter inference):

A naïvely truncated Poisson distribution, given by:

$$p_{\lambda}^{\text{naïve}}(l) = \begin{cases} \frac{\lambda^l}{l!} e^{-\lambda} + c & \text{if } \min \leq l \leq \max \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

with normalizer $c := \frac{1 - e^{-\lambda} \sum_{l=\min}^{\max} \frac{\lambda^l}{l!}}{\max - \min + 1}$

whose parameter λ conceptually directly captures the mean intron length (before truncating), and which is set to zero outside the allowed range and renormalized appropriately by a constant addend c . Recall that both the expected value and the variance of a Poisson distribution are λ . This, and Poisson-distributed variables not taking negative values, motivates the second variant of the Poisson distribution tried here: A shifted truncated Poisson distribution, given by:

$$p_{\lambda}^{\text{shifted}}(l) = \begin{cases} \frac{\lambda^{l-\min}}{(l-\min)!} e^{-\lambda} + c & \text{if } \min \leq l \leq \max \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (2.4)$$

with normalizer $c := \frac{1 - e^{-\lambda} \sum_{k=0}^{\max-\min} \frac{\lambda^k}{k!}}{\max - \min + 1}$

Which is shifted by \min to the right before truncating as above. The parameter λ then no longer directly captures the mean intron length, instead, it captures the mean excess intron length beyond the minimum length (again: before truncating). In both cases, when truncating, the summed up probabilities of all newly forbidden lengths are uniformly divided among the allowed lengths, thus slightly skewing the correspondence between λ and the mean or mean excess length.

2.5.4 Implementation

Overview

GHMM-based gene-prediction was implemented as a Java program (Java version 1.8), taking as inputs a `fasta`-file with the genome sequences (assembly contigs or chromosomes) and a `properties`-file containing the model parameters to be used when doing the predictions. This parameter-file can be written or modified by hand, and originally was, but automatic parameter inference was additionally implemented as a `jupyter notebook` (Python version 3.8.3) – inference and use of the parameters are thereby separated, allowing e.g. for a better parameter inference script/program to be written in an arbitrary language without needing to consider the concrete implementation of the gene-predictor.

The implementation of both GHMMs (implemented by the class `GHMM.java`) and Viterbi-algorithm (implemented by the classes `Viterbi.java`, and `ViterbiSeed.java` for the traceback) is per se more general than necessary for the exact model finally used, instead following Stanke^[17]'s formulation closely, with shortcuts for computational speedup added on top. Thereby, the basic implementation would also be applicable to emission-probabilities that indeed take the previous state and the emission history into account.

As usual when dealing with products of many small probabilities, these computations are instead done in logarithm (i.e. sum of many negative numbers), trying to get better numerical stability.

Speeding up the computation

As noted before, all states of the developed GHMM have very limited ranges of allowed emission lengths, with many (e.g. $\pm CDS$) allowing only exactly one emission length. Therefore, even though in general the Viterbi-algorithm requires that all emission lengths up to the current position in the sequence be considered when computing the maximum, leading to a quadratic runtime in the length of the sequence, this is unnecessary here. Instead, there is only a fixed set of emission lengths, and thus previous columns in the tabular computation of the Viterbi variables, that need to be considered when computing the maximum. Thereby, the computation of the Viterbi-variables for my GHMM can be sped up to linear runtime: Each state implements a method `iteratePermissibleLPrimes` that produces an iterator holding the valid column-indices l' which need to be considered in computing the maximum. This iterator is then used instead of looping over all $l' = 0, \dots, l - 1$ (cf. Algorithm 1), as shown in pseudocode 2.

Further, none of my states use the emission history – it can thus be

Algorithm 2: Modification to the Viterbi algorithm (Algorithm 1): Instead of iterating over all $l' = 1, \dots, l - 1$, only the relevant columns are checked. The same is done during Traceback. Note that the emission history has been replaced by `null` to avoid either unnecessary calls to `String.substring` or having to build up and store the emission history.

```

...
for  $q' \in Q$  do
  | for  $l' \in q'.\text{iteratePermissibleLPrimes}(l)$  do
  | |  $\gamma_{q,l} \leftarrow \max\{\gamma_{q,l}, \gamma_{q',l'} \cdot a_{q',q} \cdot e_{q',q,\text{null}}(\sigma[l',l])\}$ 
  | end
end
...

```

left out. In particular, naïvely constructing the emission history on the fly in Java (by calls to `String.substring`) has a linear runtime in the length of the substring/emission history (since Java 1.7.0_06^[20]), which makes the whole computation quadratic in the length of the sequence. Building up the emission history while computing the Viterbi-variables in a single String-instance instead of recomputing it every time would alleviate this problem, but the emission history is still unnecessary here, so it is left out entirely, as shown in pseudocode 2.

With these shortcuts, the implementation has practically linear runtime in the length of the input-sequence (save for any slowdown that may happen due to garbage-collection or memory leakage).

2.5.5 Inferring the parameters

The model’s parameters can largely be inferred automatically from a given annotation file (in `gff3`-format) and the annotated genomic sequence. The exceptions from this are on the one hand the estimate of the mean length of intergenic regions, which would require full annotation of the contigs/chromosomes supplied (as opposed to the partial annotation made feasible by the homology-heuristic described above). This average intergenic region size thus currently has to be manually estimated, and effectively serves as a hyperparameter influencing how strongly the model ‘wants’ to predict genes: If the mean NCS-length is set to an unrealistically low value, realistic NCS lengths become improbable, instead being interrupted by spuriously predicted genes. On the other hand, the sizes of the start-region (6nt), stop-region (24nt), and splice donor (5nt) and acceptor (4nt) sites are all to be manually decided upon. Furthermore, the ‘intron length tolerances’ t_l, t_u are a pair of hyperparameters measuring how far beyond the empirical

intron length-range an intron is allowed to lie (below the empirical minimum and above the maximum respectively), and thereby directly impact the minimum-intron-length and maximum-intron-length parameters.

With this joined input of a partially annotated genome and a number of hyperparameters, the other parameters can be inferred as follows:

NCS-parameters

Firstly, the manual estimation of the mean NCS length $\varnothing_i^{\text{NCS}}$ can be directly translated into the probability of staying in the state *NCS*, by recalling that the *NCS*-state implements a geometric length distribution with a minimum length of one:

$$\varnothing_i^{\text{NCS}} \hat{=} \mathbb{E}[L_{\text{NCS}}] = \frac{1}{1 - a_{\text{NCS},\text{NCS}}} \rightsquigarrow \hat{a}_{\text{NCS},\text{NCS}} = 1 - \frac{1}{\varnothing_i^{\text{NCS}}}$$

‘Success’ here means that *NCS* is left, hence the success-probability $1 - a_{\text{NCS},\text{NCS}}$. The base-frequencies for the emission-probabilities of *NCS* are retrieved from windows flanking the annotated genes (simply counting), with the size of this window being another hyperparameter.

Transitions from CDS

To infer the probability of staying in $\pm\text{CDS}$, the geometric length-distribution as described by the ‘success’-probability $p_{\text{end}}^{\text{exon}}$ in equation 2.1 is used: This success-probability can be estimated from the observed exon-lengths, and then yields the transition-probabilities $a_{+\text{CDS},+\text{CDS}} = a_{-\text{CDS},-\text{CDS}} = 1 - p_{\text{end}}^{\text{exon}}$. Notice however, that the geometric distribution applies only to the parts of the exons that are outside the start-ATG, stop-region and codons interrupted by introns. This has to be taken into account when retrieving the mean length of the ‘CDS’, by subtracting the respective lengths (3nt for start, 21 for stop-region without the untranslated stop-codon, 1 or 2 for the interrupted codon parts) from the actual exon-lengths. For this modified ‘CDS-length’ L (in codons), the following geometric distribution holds:

$$P([L = l]) = (1 - p_{\text{end}}^{\text{exon}})^{l-1} p_{\text{end}}^{\text{exon}} \text{ for } l \in \mathbb{N} \quad (2.5)$$

Then, the known property that the expected value $\mathbb{E}[L] = \frac{1}{p_{\text{end}}^{\text{exon}}}$ can be used to estimate $\hat{p}_{\text{end}}^{\text{exon}} = \frac{1}{\varnothing_i}$ (estimating the expected value by the empirical mean ‘CDS-length’).

Similarly, the number of introns per gene is modeled by an implicit geometric distribution, however, unlike for the CDS, there can be genes without an intron, i.e. the intron-count n takes values in \mathbb{N}_0 . ‘Success’ then means leaving $+CDS$ for $+stop$ ($-CDS$ for $-M$), while a ‘failure’ is constituted by the insertion of an intron $-$ and the number of introns n is the number of ‘failures’ before the first success (the end of the gene). Both of these prerequire that CDS be left, i.e. the probability of ‘success’ is:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{\text{exon end}}^{\text{gene end}} &= P([X_{i+1} = +stop] | [X_i = +CDS \wedge X_{i+1} \neq +CDS]) \\ &= 1 - P([X_{i+1} \in \{+intron\ 0-0, +1L, +2L\}] | [X_i = +CDS \wedge X_{i+1} \neq +CDS]) \end{aligned}$$

(analogously for the reverse strand.) It is then known that the expected number of introns per gene $\mathbb{E}[n]$ (estimated by the average number of introns per gene \varnothing_n) is given by

$$\mathbb{E}[n] = \frac{1 - p_{\text{exon end}}^{\text{gene end}}}{p_{\text{exon end}}^{\text{gene end}}} \Leftrightarrow p_{\text{exon end}}^{\text{gene end}} = \frac{1}{1 + \mathbb{E}[n]} \rightsquigarrow \hat{p}_{\text{exon end}}^{\text{gene end}} = \frac{1}{1 + \varnothing_n}$$

This conditional probability then straight-forwardly yields the transition probabilities leaving CDS as:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{+CDS,+stop} &= (1 - a_{+CDS,+CDS}) \cdot p_{\text{exon end}}^{\text{gene end}} \\ a_{+CDS,+intron\ 0-0} &= a_{+CDS,+1L} + a_{+CDS,+2L} = (1 - a_{+CDS,+CDS}) \cdot \frac{1 - p_{\text{exon end}}^{\text{gene end}}}{3} \end{aligned}$$

under the assumption that all three types of introns are equally probable/underlie no biasing selection.

Emission models of CDS and stop-region

Like the base-frequencies for NCS , the parameters $p_{i,b}^{\text{exon}}$ and $p_{i,b}^{\text{stop}}$ of the simplified codon model used by the $\pm CDS$ states and $\pm stop$ respectively, can be directly inferred by simply counting how often a base b occurs in codon position i in the coding sequences outside the stop region, and the stop-region respectively.

In addition to this codon model, the list R of exceptions therefrom in the stop-region has to be defined. Two of the corrections are manually selected based on the observations shown in the results section: TGA is entirely forbidden in this region, so it is added to R , with $q_{TGA}^{\text{stop}} = 0$. TAA too is strongly depleted, albeit not entirely absent, so it is corrected to its empirical frequency $q_{TAA}^{\text{stop}} = f_{TAA}^{\text{emp}}$, which is much lower than the probability for TAA in the simple model. Further codons could be added manually, based on some prior knowledge, however, here, two more codons are selected algorithmically. The first of these two codons is added to immediately add information, while the last serves as a compensator, so that Equation 2.2 is

satisfied.

To decide this, a target criterion is chosen: Empirically, there is a difference in codon usage between the stop-region and the previous CDS:

$$\vec{\Delta}^{\text{emp}} = \vec{f}^{\text{stop}} - \vec{f}^{\text{CDS}} \neq \vec{0}$$

where the entries of these vectors are the frequencies $f_c^{\text{stop}}, f_c^{\text{CDS}}$ of a codon c in the stop-regions and the CDS outside thereof respectively, and Δ_c^{emp} is the difference in frequency. This difference is an important signal in discerning whether a given TGA is a stop-TGA or a sense-TGA. The simplified codon models also yields such a difference (denoted by $\vec{\Delta}^{\text{simple}}$), but these need not be perfectly matched. Then, the codon for which the absolute deviation of Δ_c^{simple} from the empirical Δ_c^{emp} is maximal, is chosen and corrected:

$$\begin{aligned} c^* &= \operatorname{argmax}_{c \notin R} \left| \Delta_c^{\text{emp}} - \Delta_c^{\text{simple}} \right| = \operatorname{argmax}_{c \notin R} \left| f_c^{\text{stop}} - f_c^{\text{CDS}} - \left(\prod_{i=1}^3 p_{i,c_i}^{\text{stop}} - \prod_{i=1}^3 p_{i,c_i}^{\text{exon}} \right) \right| \\ &\rightsquigarrow c^* \in R, \text{ with } q_{c^*}^{\text{stop}} := f_{c^*}^{\text{stop}} \end{aligned}$$

Of course, this does by no means yet guarantee that the resulting probability-distribution is normalized as required in equation 2.2. Instead, there will generally be a remainder δ (with respect to the intermediate correction-set $R' = \{TGA, TAA, c^*\}$):

$$\delta := \underbrace{\sum_{c \in R'} \prod_{i=1}^3 p_{i,c_i}^{\text{stop}}}_{\text{base-wise}} - \underbrace{\sum_{c \in R'} q_c^{\text{stop}}}_{\text{corrected}}$$

Therefore, a compensator-codon c^+ is added to R , whose deviation between the base-wise model and the empirical frequency in the stop-region most closely matches this remainder δ :

$$\begin{aligned} c^+ &= \operatorname{argmin}_{c \notin R'} \left| f_c^{\text{stop}} - \prod_{i=1}^3 p_{i,c_i}^{\text{stop}} - \delta \right| \\ &\rightsquigarrow c^+ \in R, \text{ with } q_{c^+}^{\text{stop}} := \delta + \prod_{i=1}^3 p_{i,c_i^+}^{\text{stop}} \stackrel{\text{hopefully}}{\approx} f_{c^+}^{\text{stop}} \end{aligned}$$

which leads to the normalization-constraint (eq. 2.2) being fulfilled, and thus now renders R valid. This overall approach tries to keep the number of parameters small, while trying to capture $\vec{\Delta}^{\text{emp}}$ and the empirical codon frequencies in the stop-region reasonably well (a numerical example for illustration-purposes is provided in the appendix).

Emission model of the start-region

The start-region model assumes that all three bases preceding the start-ATG are drawn independently from the same categorical distribution $(p_b^{\text{start}})_{b \in \{T, C, A, G\}}$, which is estimated by counting the frequencies $f_{i,b}^{\text{start}}$ with which the bases occur in the three positions respectively, and then averaging: $p_b^{\text{start}} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{i=1}^3 f_{i,b}^{\text{start}}$. This of course takes advantage of the positions not differing pronouncedly in their nucleobase frequencies in ciliates^[24].

Intron model

The intron-model has two conceptual parts: The length distribution (a truncated shifted Poisson-distribution $p_\lambda^{\text{shifted}}(l)$), and a content-model to capture the conserved sequences of the SDS and SAS, as well as the base-usage inside the intron. To infer the parameters of the length-distribution, the lengths of all annotated introns are collected, yielding the empirical minimum and maximum length (\min_l and \max_l), and the mean length \varnothing_l . Thence, the parameter λ of $p_\lambda^{\text{shifted}}$ is estimated as $\lambda \hat{=} \varnothing_l - \min_l$. For the naïve Poisson $p_{\lambda'}^{\text{naïve}}$, it would be estimated as $\lambda' \hat{=} \varnothing_l > \lambda$. Using the ‘intron length tolerance’ hyperparameters t_l, t_u , the truncation-range is defined by $\min = \min_l - t_l$ and $\max = \max_l + t_u$.

For the content model, the sequences of the introns are collected (and transformed to be in forward direction when the intron is on the reverse strand), and the frequencies of the bases b at the different positions i in the SDS and SAS, as well as the general base-frequencies outside SDS and SAS (in the middle of the intron) are collected. This yields a number of categoricals (represented by matrices/vectors of their parameters): $p_{i,b}^{\text{SDS}}$ for the donor site, $p_{1,b}^{\text{SAS}}$ for the acceptor site, and p_b^{intron} for the middle part of the intron, with the number of positions i given by the manually set SDS-size and SAS-size respectively. It is to be expected that the canonical intron-edge-signal **GT...AG** will be clearly (potentially exclusively) represented in the first two categoricals of the SDS, and the last two of the SAS (i.e. $p_{1,G}^{\text{SDS}} = p_{2,T}^{\text{SDS}} = 1 = p_{3,A}^{\text{SAS}} = p_{4,G}^{\text{SAS}}$, or nearly so; here assuming the SAS-size to be $4nt$).

As always, when counting the occurrences of codons or bases, pseudocounts can be added to avoid overfitting to a small dataset, wherever it is biologically sensible (i.e. it is not sensible to allow TGA in the stop-region by a pseudocount, but it may be sensible to allow C in the Kozak sequence).

2.5.6 Measuring prediction-quality

Typical measures of predictive quality are the well-known sensitivity and specificity^{[11],[17]}. These require a binary understanding of the prediction, into positives and negatives – which is not immediately what gene-prediction yields. Thus, for base-wise sensitivity and specificity, nucleotides predicted to be coding are deemed positives^[17] – yielding the required numbers of true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), positives (p) and negatives (n), and thus:^[5]

$$\text{sensitivity} = \frac{\text{TP}}{p}, \quad \text{specificity} = \frac{\text{TN}}{n}$$

Stanke uses a non-standard definition of specificity, which can be formulated as $\frac{\text{TP}}{Y}$ (with $Y = \text{TP} + \text{FP}$ denoting all cases where the classifier said ‘yes’ – i.e. predicted a positive^[5]).^[17] This measure is conventionally called *precision*^[5], which will be the name used here when the precision was computed outside AUGUSTUS (using Python to parse and evaluate the predictions). Where the precision/‘specificity’ was directly computed by AUGUSTUS, it will be referred to in quotes and with reference to its origin.

However, all these measures of course give a very limited view of the predictive quality, in particular very limited to coding sequences, even though introns too should be accurately predicted (to correctly infer reading frame and connect DNA to RNA data). To better guide the design of a gene-predictor, and to more detailedly assess the prediction quality, I use *replacement matrices* (simply extending the conventional confusion matrix):

Every nucleotide in the annotated regions (which need not be the whole chromosomes) has a pair of states $(t, p) \in \{NCS, CDS, intron, stop\}^2$ – t is the nucleotide’s true state and p is the predicted state. The replacement matrix $(r_{t,p})_{t,p \in \{NCS, CDS, intron, stop\}}$ then contains the total number of occurrences of each of these pairs. There are two ways of normalizing this matrix: Normalizing the rows to sum up to one yields the ‘whither’-matrix, wherein the row t captures, what this feature got turned into (‘whither did this feature go?’), while normalizing the columns yields the ‘whence’-matrix, wherein a column p captures what features were mistaken/correctly taken for feature p (‘whence did this feature come?’). Ideally of course, the replacement-matrix would be diagonal, and then be normalized to yield the identity-matrix.

Alternatively, and here additionally, to assessing the prediction quality on a nucleotide level, it can also be measured on a feature-level, i.e. with respect to whole exons or introns. In this case, a true positive is an almost entirely correctly predicted feature (same type of feature, same strand, same start, same end; translation frame is ignored for exons). The number of

positives (p) then is the total number of features of the considered type in the annotation, and the number of predicted positives (Y) is the total number of features of this class in the prediction, that overlap with or lie entirely within the annotated regions. Negatives are not easily defined in this case, so on a feature-level, sensitivity and precision will be given.

Chapter 3

Results

3.1 Characterizing the difference between sense- and stop-UGA

7111 of the transcriptome-assembly's contigs ended in seven or more consecutive adenines – these form the basis of the subsequent results. For 665 of these 7111 transcripts, at least four of the top ten (or all of the hits, if there are less than ten hits) were within 6aa of the putative stop-UGA – which is the dataset used for figures 3.1 B and 3.2, and for 244, all top ten (or all, if less than ten hits in total) hits were within this range. The latter dataset is used for figure 3.1 A.

3.1.1 General sequence-features

3' UTR lengths As shown in figure 3.1 A, the 3'UTRs generally have a quite narrow, at least roughly unimodal length-distribution, with only a very small number of long UTRs. The smallest identified UTR is 9nt long, while the largest is 1110nt. Overall, the UTRs are fairly short, with an average length of $\bar{x} \approx 50.2\text{nt}$, a median of $Q_2 = 41\text{nt}$, and a standard deviation of $\sigma \approx 76.5\text{nt}$. This fits with the mechanism previously proposed to explain how the cell tells sense- from stop-UTR^[19], as the poly-A-tail, and hence, any poly-A-binding-proteins, will be quite close to the inferred stop-UGA.

Base frequencies in CDS versus 3' UTR A marked %GC drop-off was observed at the inferred stop-UGA, from 33.5%GC in CDS to 18.6% in 3'UTR, which is plainly visible in figure 3.1 B, and mainly due to an enrichment of U (30.2% \rightarrow 45.9%) and a corresponding depletion of G (19.5% \rightarrow 8.5%), and to a lesser extent of C (14% \rightarrow 10.2%).

Figure 3.1: **A** Unnormalised histogram of the 3' UTR-lengths as inferred by the heuristic: The lengths ranged from 9nt to 1110nt, with median-length $Q_2 = 41nt$, and mean length $\varnothing_l \approx 50.2nt$. **B** Base-frequencies around the putative stop: The stop-UGA is clearly visible by the 100% U at position 0 (where stop-UGA's U is), and following 100% G and 100% A. Compared to the CDS to the left, G is markedly depleted, U is markedly enriched in the UTR, with A and C following the same trend towards lower %GC in the UTR less pronouncedly. Note further the enrichment of G in the first codon-position in the CDS, resulting in a peak of G-frequency every three nucleotides, which is mainly compensated by a dip in U's frequency. Naturally, this codon-structure is absent from the UTR.

Additionally, G is periodically enriched in the CDS, with every third nucleotide having a notably increased probability of being G, and a reduced probability of being U. This occurs on the first base of the inframe-codons, reflecting the non-uniform codon-usage (but marginalized over the other two positions respectively). Such a codon structure is absent from the 3' UTR (see figure 3.1 B: Pronounced zigzag vs. no/barely any zigzag of the red line), as the latter is not organized in codons. Since they do not reflect any biological information (at least approximately) but are instead just random fluctuations, the base-frequency-results for the UTR also visualize the level of random noise as arisen from the underlying biological noise and the sample-size.

3.1.2 Depletion of UGA and UAA before stop-UGA

In line with previous findings^[19], a depletion of UGA in the reading-frame right upstream of the stop-UGA was observed, as shown in figure 3.2 A. However, there are some transcripts (17 of the 665) which have at least one UGA closely upstream of the heuristically predicted stop. In these cases, some of the hits extend beyond the earlier UGA, but it stands to reason that

the earlier is the actual stop and the heuristic simply fails. In particular, in multiple of these cases, a fairly large number of low-scoring hits end right of the more reasonable stop-UGA, and then lead to a later UGA being the putative stop.

The notable asymmetry near 0 in Figure 3.2 E is due to these few cases, introducing a few UGA-occurrences downstream of the sense-UGA at position 0, which are deemed stops by the heuristic. Further away, the symmetry is visible. There is clearly no depletion of UGA before sense-UGA, i.e. this very depletion is sequence-signal differentiating stop- from sense-UGA. The exact driving force of this depletion is however not yet known^[19], and internal communication.

Other codons, such as the generally abundant AAA (coding for Lysine^[4], see figure 3.2 C), are not depleted before the stop-UGA, but do show a change in frequency between CDS and 3'UTR, which reflects both the absence of a codon-structure of the UTR, and the %GC of the codon in question. AAA has a %GC of 0, and is thus enriched in the GC-poor UTR (recall figure 3.1), and additionally is the only codon found in the poly-A-tail, which may additionally boost its abundance here. There is exactly one exception to this general pattern: the unambiguously repurposed stop-codon UAA is also depleted before stop-UGA, albeit not as cleanly as UGA. This is in contrast to the behaviour of the other unambiguously repurposed stop-codon UAG (compare figures 3.2 B and D), which like UAA codes for glutamine (Q) in karyorelicts like *Loxodes*^[4].

One might then suspect that UAA too is actually an ambiguous stop-codon, coding for either Q or stop, with much the same behaviour as UGA, just used more rarely. However, applying the same heuristic to find 'stop'-UAA for one yields much fewer results of sufficient quality (in terms of the number of top-10 hits near the putative 'stop'-UAA), and even for these 168 transcripts, where *three* of the ten best hits were within 6aa from the 'stop', no depletion of UAA can be found upstream of the 'stop'-UAA (see figure 3.2 F). Thus, the depletion of UGA and UAA is a phenomenon limited to stop-UGA, with UAA probably never being used as a stop-codon in *Loxodes*/karyorelicts, and definitely not showing the same sequence-patterns as UGA.

Comparison to other ciliates Two ciliate species, for which annotations of direct useability were available on ciliates.org (and its adjoined sites)^[18], were used to look for codon-depletion upstream of stop-codons: *Tetrahymena thermophila* uses an unambiguous variant genetic code with UAA and UAG repurposed to code for Q, while the more closely *Loxodes*-related *Stentor coeruleus* uses the standard genetic code. *Stentor* then serves only as a control for the

Figure 3.2: Absolute numbers of codon-occurrences in a set of 665 transcripts, for which four of the top ten hits were within 6aa of the putative stop: **A** occurrences of UGA around stop-UGA as identified by the heuristic. Note that the y-axis is clipped to a maximum of 14, with the bar at codon position 0 extending to 665. **B** UAA before stop-UGA, **C** example of an arbitrary codon around stop-UGA: AAA is not depleted at all, but due to its low %GC is abundant in the UTR (where the poly-A-tail may additionally be mistaken for UTR) – codons beside UGA and UAA in general show this pattern: Near unchanged presence before stop-UGA, and then increase or decrease of abundance in the UTR based on their %GC, **D** UAG (conventional stop-codon, unambiguously repurposed in *Karyorelictea*) before stop-UGA, **E** UGA around sense-UGA, **F** UAA before pseudo-stop UAA (identified by applying the heuristic and searching for UAA instead of UGA)

Figure 3.3: Relative abundance of the stop-codons UGA, UAA and UAG in two ciliates with unambiguous genetic codes: *Tetrahymena thermophila*, which uses only UGA as a stop (and only as such), with UAA and UAG coding for Q. *Stentor coeruleus* is more closely related to *Loxodes magnus* than *Tetrahymena* is^[7], but uses the standard genetic code.^[19] *Stentor* serves merely as a control of the processing steps, as none of the stop-codons can occur in the reading frame (exactly as seen in the bottom row). *Tetrahymena* does not show a depletion of UAA before the stop-codon, but of course, UGA cannot occur in-frame either. Note that the top left plot is clipped, with the orange bar reaching all the way to 1 (all stops are UGA).

processing: No stop-codons can exist in-frame upstream of the stop. To fulfill this requirement, such genes where an intron or other noncoding segment is within the sampled range have to be excluded, otherwise, one indeed finds occurrences of ‘in-frame’ stops (which are outside CDS, but within the sampled window) upstream of the actual stop in *Stentor* and *Tetrahymena*. Having used *Stentor* to identify this problem, and having excluded the respective genes, the resulting codon-usage is shown in figure 3.3: The two repurposed stop-codons in *Tetrahymena* show no depletion upstream of the stop-UGA, hinting at this depletion being biologically meaningful in *Loxodes*.

3.1.3 Verifying the heuristic using conserved proteins

As shown in figure 3.4, using a set of 42 highly conserved proteins (core histones and ribosomal proteins, listed in appendix) from *Tetrahymena* (for which

such annotation was available) as a basis to identify stop-UGA from homology information yields very similar results to using a much larger dataset of ciliate proteins of various degrees of conservation (145 transcripts had sufficiently high-scoring matches to the 42 conserved proteins). The 3'UTR-lengths were found to be a bit larger on average (and in median), and the base-frequencies are so noisy that statements about intra-codon-positional biases are hard to make (due to the verification-dataset being much smaller), but most importantly, none of the acquired statistics clearly contradicted the previous findings: The homology heuristic seems to be sufficiently stable against unconserved proteins (with more random/less informative hits). Recall that the heuristic does not directly use any information about UGA-depletion, UTR-length or base-composition, rendering the agreement of the results relevant.

3.1.4 No clear motifs around stop-UGA

The constructed PWMs (visualised as heat-maps in figure 3.5, and listed as tables in supplementary table A.1) all have pairwise distances $d < 0.2$ (the distances are: sense \leftrightarrow stop ≈ 0.0323 , sense \leftrightarrow utr ≈ 0.0694 , stop \leftrightarrow utr ≈ 0.0548) – and visually inspecting them mainly reveals the above-described pattern of G-preference in the first position of a codon within the coding sequence, and the absence of such codon-structure in the UTR. Thus, while there seems not to be a clear sequence-motif (other than poly-A^[19]) that would discriminate stop-UGA from sense-UGA, the difference between CDS and NCS already partially captured by the used prior can still be used for gene-prediction.

3.2 Manual annotation

A total of 154 genes on 141 contigs were annotated manually in a first round of annotation, and served as a training and testing-dataset (being randomly split into the two) for AUGUSTUS and my own predictor. Of these, 2 were excluded (for one, the contig still contained N, i.e. it was incomplete, and for the other, the introns were not well-supported by the read-coverage), yielding 152 used genes. These 152 genes could therefore not serve as a final benchmark. After both AUGUSTUS and my predictor had been tested and improved/‘optimized’ on this first dataset, some 52 more genes were annotated and served as the benchmark-dataset used for the results shown in tables 3.1, 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4.

Since I rely on quite limited homology-information, the resulting annotation is very sparse/incomplete, with most contigs whereon any gene is annotated only featuring a single annotated gene, although, going by the contig-wide read-coverage, there would be more genes on the contig. However, annotating without homology-information would have meant that the

Figure 3.4: Found statistics based on the highly conserved proteins: **A** histogram of the 3'UTR-lengths: the lengths reached from 17nt to 483nt, with a mean-length of $\varnothing \approx 58.6$ nt, and median $Q_2 = 47$ nt. Compared to the result shown in figure 3.1 A, the UTRs seem to be a bit longer here. **B** base-frequencies around the stop-UGA: Note the much higher noise-level compared to figure 3.1 B. The overall result still is visibly much the same. **C** occurrences of UGA around the stop-UGA and **D** occurrences of UAA around stop-UGA. Note the larger window compared to figure 3.2, and note that the UGA-free region is notably bigger here. Still, both codons seem to be depleted before the stop-UGA.

Figure 3.5: Heatmap visualisation of the PWMs constructed around sense-UGA, stop-UGA, and 3'UTR-UGA: the respective UGA's G is at position 0. Note the repeated pattern especially visible around sense-UGA, and to a lesser extent before stop-UGA, showing a preference for G in the first position of a codon (in the last row respectively). Such a preference is absent from the UTR-UGA, since it is flanked by non-coding sequence without a codon-structure. Curiously, the largest $W_{b,i}$ are found in the UTR-heatmap

stop-UGA would have had to be guessed, at which point the value of such an annotation for training a gene-predictor is very questionable.

The number of UGA-codons found in the reading-frame vs. outside thereof was counted, with the corresponding histograms of the total counts per gene shown in figure 3.6. Clearly, the occurrence of sense-UGA is not a rare exception that would only marginally cause problems to a conventional gene-predictor, but one can expect to find one or more sense-UGAs in a given gene. On average, 10.63 sense-UGAs are found in a gene (median: 9), and 20.25 UGAs (median: 16) are found in the two untranslated frames – i.e. UGA is not markedly depleted from the reading frame when compared to the non-reading frames (of which there are two), when comparing to an oversimple uniform model, by which there would be ≈ 2 UGAs outside the reading frame for every sense-UGA.

Figure 3.6: Statistics about the annotated genes (only the 152 genes in the training-set): Unnormalised histograms of **A** number of sense-UGAs, **B** number of UGAs outside the reading-frame, **C** exon lengths (actual exon lengths, not the truncated lengths used for parameter-estimation), and **D** number of introns found in each gene. The medians are marked in red (A: 9, B: 16, C: 958.5, D: 0), and the average is marked by the dashed line (and given as \varnothing in the plots).

3.3 Testing Augustus on the annotation

3.3.1 Moderately poor, understated performance

Simply training AUGUSTUS on the final 152-gene training-set, and then testing on the 52-gene test-set shows a moderately poor performance, as summarized in tables 3.1 and 3.2, especially with respect to nucleotide-level sensitivity (the results are similar for randomised training/testing-splits of the final training-set). Inspecting the predictions in Geneious shed further light on the difficulties encountered by the program: AUGUSTUS clearly has trouble predicting the reliably very short introns found in *Loxodes* and other ciliates, and may opt to predict an intron where an in-frame UGA would occur, so as to bridge that stop-codon, as shown in figure 3.7. This can be seen both in the structure of the prediction (visual inspection) and in the low intron-to-intron-value in the ‘whence’-matrices in table 3.2: Only a minority of the nucleotides that are predicted to be in introns indeed come from introns – while most of the bases predicted to be intronic should really be coding

(table 3.2 A). What is not captured by the quality-measures listed in tables 3.1 and 3.2 is any deviation of the predicted reading frame from the actual one – again from visual inspection, it can be inferred that AUGUSTUS may choose the wrong frame (it even occasionally picks the wrong strand) in a region of heightened %GC, so as to avoid in-frame UGA, but still predict a gene based on the %GC and codon-structure found in the sequence.

Figure 3.7: Visualisation (using Geneious^[8]) of an example (Node 748 of the assembly) of the problems facing AUGUSTUS: CDS/exons are marked in yellow, the gene predicted by AUGUSTUS is marked in green, introns are marked in black (and 3'UTR in white, start and stop codon in light blue, transcript as predicted by AUGUSTUS in beige). UGAs in the frame of the leftmost CDS predicted by AUGUSTUS are marked by black rectangles above the annotation. The ‘true’ annotation (based on homology information and read coverage) is shown in the top-row (and covers a longer stretch of the sequence than the gene predicted by AUGUSTUS). Note that the leftmost in-frame UGA is the one AUGUSTUS (wrongly) deems to be the stop, and that there are two UGAs in this same frame where AUGUSTUS predicted the intron (and similarly, but not shown, there is a single UGA inside the intron that would be in the frame of the rightmost CDS). AUGUSTUS here emblematically predicts an overlong intron to evade UGAs, and then has to pick somewhat arbitrary start- and stop-points for its prediction, that do not agree well with the actual gene.

However, still, due to AUGUSTUS using a nonstandard measure of specificity, it somewhat understates its predictive power: Compare the conventional measure of specificity as given in table 3.1 to the specificity given by the software itself. The actual predictions are much better than what the program’s output (and naming thereof) would suggest on the nucleotide level. On the feature-level however, the predictions border on uselessness, as shown in table 3.4, with AUGUSTUS particularly struggling to identify any introns correctly (a problem not limited to *Loxodes*, but extending to other ciliates like *Blepharisma* too [internal communication: Minakshi Singh]).

	window [nt]		nucleotide-level			exon-level	
	up	down	sensitivity	specificity	AUGUSTUS-‘specificity’	sensitivity	precision
unmodified			0.693	0.993	0.533	0.317	0.408
base	12	12	0.901	0.954	0.446	0.258	0.304
base	18	18	0.922	0.963	0.413	0.348	0.418
base	18	24	0.931	0.966	0.411	0.470	0.564
base	24	18	0.923	0.958	0.410	0.348	0.418
base	24	24	0.932	0.966	0.413	0.485	0.582
codon	12	12	0.908	0.942	0.384	0.091	0.111
codon	18	18	0.938	0.952	0.386	0.152	0.182
codon	18	24	0.941	0.963	0.399	0.318	0.389
codon	24	18	0.939	0.947	0.379	0.152	0.182
codon	24	24	0.934	0.957	0.398	0.303	0.377

Table 3.1: Measures of predictive performance of AUGUSTUS on unmodified sequences, and applied to simplistically preprocessed sequences: ‘base’ refers to the case where a base-wise (not codon-wise) model was used to identify sense-UGA, while ‘codon’ refers to the codon-wise model. The window-size upstream and downstream of the UGA in question is given in nucleotides in the columns ‘up’ and ‘down’. The sensitivity and specificity, and exon-level sensitivity and precision were computed outside AUGUSTUS in a Python-script, according to their conventional definition^[5]. Additionally, the ‘specificity’ as computed and printed by AUGUSTUS itself is given. Column-maxima are given in boldface.

3.3.2 Simplistic preprocessing does not yield convincing results

Using a very simple probabilistic model to ‘clean’ sense-UGA from the sequences yields a non-trivial change to the predictive performance: While the sensitivity is markedly increased (i.e. more of the nucleotides in CDS are correctly identified as such), both the specificity, and the ‘specificity’ computed by AUGUSTUS are slightly decreased. Similarly, visually inspecting the resulting predictions does not give a clear picture of improvement, instead, quite a chaotic image arises, probably due to the simple preprocessing being too simple, and wrongly deleting stop-UGA, while also wrongly keeping sense-UGA (both of which it does) – thereby it mainly adds more noise. This is not clear from the sensitivity and specificity measures alone, which look reasonable (see table 3.1), and only somewhat visible in the exon-level measures shown in tables 3.1 and 3.4. Among the tested preprocessing-steps, applying the base-wise model with a symmetric 24nt upstream and downstream window yielded the best exon-level performance, while the results for nucleotide-level performance are less clear. Note in particular that preprocessing using the codon-wise model actually consistently decreases the exon-level sensitivity (while increasing the nucleotide-level sensitivity), and has an inconsistent effect on the exon-level precision.

Since this did not yield a convincing solution (especially upon visual inspection), more complicated preprocessing, taking the reading frame into

A									
whither	NCS	CDS	intron	stop	whence	NCS	CDS	intron	stop
NCS	0.90915	0.00932	0.08153	0.0	NCS	0.71063	0.00778	0.33422	0.0
CDS	0.21292	0.69267	0.0937	0.00071	CDS	0.28517	0.99027	0.65811	0.26087
intron	0.50211	0.29114	0.20675	0.0	intron	0.00316	0.00196	0.00683	0.0
stop	0.26531	0.0	0.04082	0.69388	stop	0.00104	0.0	0.00084	0.73913

B									
whither	NCS	CDS	intron	stop	whence	NCS	CDS	intron	stop
NCS	0.89775	0.03392	0.06804	0.00029	NCS	0.93081	0.02044	0.54247	0.06977
CDS	0.03665	0.93184	0.0314	0.00011	CDS	0.06614	0.97714	0.43564	0.04651
intron	0.31395	0.41085	0.27519	0.0	intron	0.00274	0.00209	0.0185	0.0
stop	0.05882	0.11111	0.08497	0.7451	stop	0.0003	0.00033	0.00339	0.88372

Table 3.2: ‘Whither’ and ‘whence’ matrices for the Swart-Lab-AUGUSTUS-variant without preprocessing (**A**), and when preprocessing with the base-wise model and window-sizes 24nt and 24nt (**B**, cf. table 3.1). Note that in both cases, only a minority of those bases predicted to be in an intron actually are in an intron (for basic AUGUSTUS, the majority of these bases should have been CDS, and for the corrected one, the majority should have been non-coding; ‘whence’-matrices). Further note in all four matrices the high CDS→CDS values that give rise to the good predictive quality-indicators as listed in table 3.1: Most coding bases are indeed predicted to be coding, and of those bases predicted to be coding, almost all actually are. The preprocessing notably improves the earlier: more of the coding bases are correctly recognized when preprocessing the sequences. This gives no information about whether the frame is correctly predicted.

account, was expected to be necessary. However, at that point – when inferring the reading frame and taking care of introns – one already is doing gene prediction. Thus, full-on gene prediction independent of the existing AUGUSTUS-implementation, was next tried (AUGUSTUS understating its predictive power played an important role in this decision, as the deviation from the convention was only later noticed).

3.4 A custom GHMM for gene prediction in *Loxodes*

3.4.1 General performance

The GHMM-based gene-predictor developed here again does not yield trivially superior predictions compared to AUGUSTUS combined with preprocessing: Trained on a randomly chosen training-set of the same size as the one used to train AUGUSTUS, it reaches a sensitivity of 99.15%, better than any of the AUGUSTUS-variants, but a specificity of only 92.80% – which is worse than any of the AUGUSTUS-variants. Similar results are obtained when training on the full 152-gene training-set and testing the prediction on the 52

whither	NCS	CDS	intron	stop	whence	NCS	CDS	intron	stop
NCS	0.89439	0.10423	0.0008	0.00058	NCS	0.97703	0.05819	0.10204	0.10345
CDS	0.01194	0.988	0.0	0.00006	CDS	0.02227	0.94144	0.0	0.01724
intron	0.06589	0.0814	0.85271	0.0	intron	0.0006	0.00038	0.89796	0.0
stop	0.01923	0.0	0.0	0.98077	stop	0.00011	0.0	0.0	0.87931

Table 3.3: Performance of my predictor as captured by the ‘whither’ and ‘whence’-matrices, when inferring the parameters on the complete training-set of the annotation (152 genes; the same genes as the ones used for the results shown in table 3.1) and then testing the performance on the remaining test-set (52 genes). The nucleotide-level sensitivity was 0.988 (higher than any of the AUGUSTUS variants), and the specificity 0.901 (lower than any of the AUGUSTUS-variants). Notice the better intron-predictions already indicated in the matrices

benchmark-genes, as seen in the comparison in table 3.4.

Visually inspecting does however show that the custom GHMM is very fit to handle the difference between sense- and stop-UGA, with predicted gene-structures very closely matching the annotated ones. This can also quantitatively be seen in the replacement-matrix/‘whither’ and ‘whence’ matrices shown in table 3.3: The majority of bases in introns are correctly identified (‘whither’ intron→intron $\approx 85.3\%$), and the majority of the bases predicted to be in introns actually are (‘whence’ intron→intron $\approx 89.8\%$). Similarly, the diagonal values for NCS, CDS and stop-codons are all well over 50% (rendering the matrices fairly diagonal). Still, the GHMM clearly struggles with correctly telling CDS from introns, as can be seen by the fairly large proportion of bases predicted to be intronic, but actually coming from exons (‘whence’ CDS→intron), as well as the large proportion of intron-bases mispredicted to be coding (‘whither’ intron→CDS).

Additionally, the exon- and especially the intron-level sensitivity and precision show a massive improvement over the predictions made by the AUGUSTUS-variants, as shown in table 3.4: Not only does the custom GHMM predict any introns correctly at all (which all AUGUSTUS-variants fail to do), but correctly finds a majority of the annotated introns (intron-sensitivity $\approx 87\%$), while also not making large amounts of wrong intron-predictions (intron-precision $\approx 93\%$). Thus, while on a nucleotide-level, the improvement of the prediction is hard to grasp, on a feature-level it is rather pronounced, moving the prediction from hardly informative to reasonable.

3.4.2 Parameter-estimates

Though varying somewhat with the exact training-set used, the GC-content of NCS was found to be about 23%, with T and A, and G and C respectively having nearly the same frequency – as is expected from a stretch of sequence

predictor	nucleotide-level		exon-level		intron-level	
	sens.	spec.	sens.	prec.	sens.	prec.
A AUGUSTUS	0.693	0.993	0.317	0.408	0.0	0.0
B base (24/24)	0.932	0.966	0.485	0.582	0.0	0.0
C codon (18/24)	0.941	0.963	0.318	0.389	0.0	0.0
D custom GHMM	0.988	0.901	0.848	0.691	0.867	0.929

Table 3.4: Comparison of the performance of the Swart-Lab-variant of AUGUSTUS without preprocessing (**A**), with base-wise preprocessing (24nt upstream, 24nt downstream, **B**) and with codon-wise preprocessing (18nt upstream, 24nt downstream, **C**) – chosen based on the comparison shown in table 3.1, to the performance of my predictor (**D**). The sensitivity and specificity on the nucleotide-level (w.r.t. coding nucleotides, cf. table 3.1), and the sensitivity and precision on a whole-feature-level w.r.t. exons and introns respectively are given (rounded to three decimals). All AUGUSTUS-variants failed to predict even a single intron perfectly, which is likely to introduce undesirable frame-shifts into the predicted gene-sequence. The GHMM developed here meanwhile predicted the majority of exons and introns correctly. Here, it can be seen that the base-wise UGA-cleaning approach seems to introduce the better overall prediction, though it still performs poorly on the feature-level.

that does not belong to either the forward or reverse strand. This symmetry then serves as a ‘sanity-check’ of the annotation.

The GC-content found in the CDS (outside the stop-region) meanwhile was about ten percent higher at 33%, with G being about twice as frequent in the first codon-position ($f_{1,G} \approx 29\%$) as in the second or third position ($f_{2,G} \approx 15\%$, $f_{3,G} \approx 14\%$). The coding sequences of course are either on the forward or reverse strand, and thus no symmetry of the base-frequencies is expected or found here. The results for the stop-region are similar, though the sample-size is smaller (less codons can be considered in total), and hence the results are a little less stable. The bias towards G in the first position seems to be slightly weaker in the stop-region ($f_{1,G}^{\text{stop}} \approx 25\%$ vs $f_{2,G}^{\text{stop}} \approx f_{3,G}^{\text{stop}} \approx 12 - 17\%$). Similarly unstable across different choices of the training-set are the algorithmically chosen two additional codons c^* and c^+ , which e.g. are chosen as $c^+ = TTC$ or $c^+ = TAC$. These choices of course depends on the empirical codon-frequencies in the fairly small stop-regions (sample size: seven codons per annotated gene), and are hence subject to considerable noise. Since the identity of these additional correction-codons, as opposed to the *a priori*-picked TGA and TAA, does not reflect some general biological pattern in *Loxodes*, the choice being more or less random does not matter much, since it in any case does render the corrected emission-distribution of $\pm stop$ more closely fit to the observations.

A base-wise approximation of codon-frequencies can mostly capture the codon-usage

Even though it does not capture the statistical dependencies that exist between the bases in a codon, the base-wise approximation used for both the emission probabilities of $\pm CDS$ and $\pm stop$ is reasonable, especially considering how much fewer parameters are needed. As can be seen in figure 3.8, the approximation does mostly preserve the qualitative relations between the codons – though far from perfectly so, while also stopping rare codons which by pure chance were never seen in the training-set from being forbidden altogether, without a need for pseudo-counts. The situation for the stop-region-model is similar, though four of the codons are explicitly forced to their empirical frequencies, which of course reduces the difference.

Figure 3.8: Comparison of the empirical codon-frequencies found in the annotated coding sequences (outside the stop-regions; no pseudocounts included; blue) and the approximation thereof as resulting from assuming statistical independence between the positions of a codon (orange). Clearly, information is lost when assuming statistical independence, as the fit is far from perfect, with many codons over- or underestimated. However, the approximation generally captures the tendencies of the codons (frequent codons still are frequent, rare still are rare), but does mix some codons up: e.g. GGA is much less probable under the approximation than GTA, while empirically being much more common.

Realistic intron-prediction

The observed number of introns per gene (figure 3.6) plausibly fits the geometric distribution described in equation 2.1. Therefore, the way introns

are modelled in the GHMM (figure 2.1) is not only conceptually and mathematically convenient, but also fit to the observed biological reality.

For the length distribution, of the ones tried here (strict empirical, untruncated Poisson, a custom distribution formed by piecing together other distributions – which is not detailed here because it is overcomplicated and not of any use, and the distributions specified in equations 2.3 and 2.4), the shifted and truncated Poisson-distribution yielded the best results. It also is visually reminiscent of the empirical length-distribution, as shown in figure 3.9, though less sharp, and of course has the great advantage of lending itself to easy parameter-estimation.

The resulting intron-predictions are very fit to the annotation, often matching perfectly, as shown by the intron-level sensitivity and precision shown in table 3.4. The length-distribution alone would not suffice to yield such good intron-predictions, as can be seen in figure 3.10.

3.4.3 Contribution of the model's parts

The change made by incorporating part of the Kozak-sequence into the start-state ('new start'), incorporating the SDS and SAS beyond the outermost two bases ('new intron'), and modelling the codon-usage in the stop-region not by the empirical codon-usage (with pseudocounts on every codon except UGA), but by a simplified model assuming mostly statistical independence of the codon's bases ('new stop'), respectively and in combination, are shown in figure 3.10. The model was here trained on a randomly chosen subset (same for all variants) of 58 genes (on 55 contigs) and tested on the remaining genes of the overall 'training' dataset. The final testing-dataset was not used, because these model-optimizations were made based on the feedback gotten from running it on the training-set. The changes thus reflect (but do not log in exact detail) the gradual improvements made to the model when designing and testing it.

Clearly, the simplified, less closely fit stop-region-model yields quite a drastic improvement of the prediction, by enabling the predictor to better identify stop-UGA, even when the (here quite small) training-dataset is too small to estimate the 64 parameters of the empirical codon-usage with acceptable quality. With the correct stop identified, the rest of the prediction has an 'anchor' to rely on, thus, all measures of prediction-quality improve pronouncedly, even though they may not immediately be connected to the correct stop being found. Without the better stop-model, changing the other two model-parts does not yield any convincing improvements. This is quite expected for the intron-model, which does not really contribute to inferring

Figure 3.9: Different possible choices for the intron state’s emission-length distribution, with the empirical mean $\varnothing_l \approx 17.8$ marked by the dashed line: Clearly, the strict empirical distribution (not including pseudocounts) of the intron-lengths would lead to blind overfitting to a usually small dataset. Note e.g. here that the intron-lengths 24 and 25 are not present in the dataset, while 26 is – which is random chance, and not a reflection of the biology. Two truncated Poisson-distributions are also given (as defined in Equations 2.3 and 2.4): Both strictly forbid any intron of a length smaller than the minimum ($\min_l = 12$) or larger than the maximum ($\max_l = 30$), and are actual probability distributions (sum to 1). The naïvely truncated Poisson distribution uses exactly the empirical mean intron length for its parameter λ – which also means that its variance λ (before truncating) takes a rather large value, rendering the distribution quite flat. The shifted Poisson distribution instead uses $\lambda = \varnothing_l - \min_l$, and is shifted by \min_l to the right, thus being narrower and more fit to the empirical distribution.

where a gene starts or ends, and thereby does not yield ‘anchors’, where one feature can be predicted with good confidence, from which the gene-prediction could extend. However, the start-state should yield such reliable ‘anchors’ much like the stop-state, but here does not. This indicates that the start-model still could be extended, akin to the larger start-region-model used by AUGUSTUS^[17], and that the current start-model is quite minimalist (if not insufficient).

Once the stop-region-model is improved however, the other two model-changes have a more measureable positive effect, with the intron-model expectably particularly improving the intron-level (and thereby indirectly the exon-level) sensitivity and precision.

Figure 3.10: Contribution of the stop-model, the start-model and the intron model. Predictive performance is given as tables showing nucleotide-level sensitivity and specificity in the first row, exon-level sensitivity and *precision* in the second, and intron-level sensitivity and precision in the third, all in percent (rounded to whole percent; the format is also specified in the template-table on the left). The ‘old’ intron model does not use any intron-specific sequence-information (SDS, SAS, internal makeup), and relies solely on the length-distribution and the **GT...AG**-intron-edges. The ‘old’ stop-region-model uses an empirical codon-usage-categorical (with pseudocounts except on UGA; i.e. 64 parameters) for its emission probabilities. The ‘old’ start region only demands a start-AUG, but does not consider the Kozak-consensus sequence.

Chapter 4

Discussion and Outlook

4.1 Modelling choices

In contrast to AUGUSTUS, which explicitly models the exon-length distribution in the exon-states^[17], the GHMM presented here uses an implicit shifted geometric length distribution: The minimum exon-length here is 3nt for an internal exon consisting of a single uninterrupted codon between two introns. While this is biologically implausible, it does render the model less complex. Even with such unrealistically short internal exons, the model requires a minimum concatenated CDS-length of 27nt due to the start codon and stop-region having fixed sizes outside the geometric distribution implemented by $\pm CDS$. Still, the model relies more on sequence-information – codon-usage, %GC and conserved sequences – to identify exons than on a realistic length-distribution. For introns, the model here presented again uses a simpler approach than AUGUSTUS, but this time by avoiding an implicit geometrical length distribution. This latter decision is motivated by three main reasons: one is the modelled biological reality of very short introns in *Loxodes* and other ciliates, the second purpose of this explicitness is trying to prevent the model from placing introns over any inconvenient stretch of sequence, i.e. making the model more restrictive, and lastly, since introns can introduce frame-shifts (unlike exons), they should be very reliably predicted for the overall gene-prediction to be more useful.

Nonetheless, adding an explicit, fit model of exon-lengths into the $\pm CDS$ states, and differentiating between initial, internal and final exons beyond the presence of a start-codon at the head of all initial exons, and the presence of a stop-region in final exons, should likely yield better predictions. Similarly, extending the start-region states to capture the whole Kozak-consensus-sequence and the initial part of the first exon, as done in the model of AUGUSTUS^[17], is expected to improve the results, by providing a reliable ‘anchor’ akin to

the stop-region, that could guide the model to predict a more biologically realistic gene. However, the additional parameters necessarily introduced in making the model more detailed probably generally will require a larger training-dataset to be estimated with reasonable confidence.

In terms of the number of necessary parameters, the Poisson-distribution used to model the intron-length is very elegant, however, the estimation of the parameter λ is suboptimal here: Since the distribution is truncated, and the resulting distribution normalized by adding a uniform weight over all allowed values, the actual expected value differs (slightly) from λ . This could be fixed by analytically deriving the correct expected value and solving for λ . However, with the construction presented here, this is quite nontrivial, and was thus deemed beyond the scope of this thesis, in particular, since the heuristic estimate yields a very reasonable fit to the empirical intron-length distribution.

Likewise, the decision to correct four codons in particular is not motivated by any mathematical rigour, but is the result of a purely heuristic balancing of the number of included parameters and the exactness of the fit. From the prior biological knowledge gained about the depletion of UGA and UAA, it was clear that some number of codons (at least these two) had to be corrected to different frequencies than those the simple base-wise model yields. Since the changes made to UGA and UAA's probability do not cancel, for both are depleted compared to the base-wise model, another codon would also have to be corrected simply to cancel the correction made to UGA and UAA, and this codon would need have its frequency underestimated by the base-wise model. Visual inspection then showed that indeed there were some pronouncedly underestimated codons, that would directly warrant correction even if they did not fully and exactly cancel the corrections made to UGA and UAA. Therefore, one such codon was included to mainly add information to the model, and a fourth codon was taken to strictly be the compensator for the remaining deviation of the corrected frequencies from the base-wise frequencies. Of course, more codons could be included, which was not tried out here, maybe improving the prediction. However, more explicitly corrected codons of course also make overfitting easier, and from the results obtained with the four codons corrected, it would seem that the stop-region is not the main remaining problem of the GHMM (start region is more plausible).

4.2 Improvement over Augustus and limits

Clearly, the predictor developed here outperforms AUGUSTUS on *Loxodes magnus* with respect to feature-level measures of predictive quality. By contrast, the less informative nucleotide-level measures are not clearly in favour of the custom GHMM, with the specificity of the custom GHMM being inferior to that of any AUGUSTUS-variant tried here. Notably, the second-most promising candidate for predicting genes in *Loxodes* (base-wise correction/preprocessing-heuristic with 24nt window up- and downstream, table 3.4) tried out here also has a lower nucleotide-level specificity compared to AUGUSTUS without preprocessing, while achieving better exon-level sensitivity and precision. None of the performance-measures used here take reading-frame into account, although that would be quite informative, but the intron-level sensitivity and precision clearly show where all AUGUSTUS-variants fail: Correctly predicting introns. This problem is alleviated, although not fully solved, by the GHMM presented here.

Judging from visual inspection, AUGUSTUS generally predicts single-exon genes quite well, especially if they lack in-frame stops (which some do), and only really produces highly dubious results when introns come into play, with introns being inserted to bridge in-frame stops or shift the reading frame into one where no UGA-codon occurs for a given segment, and the edges of actual introns being not generally well-predicted.

Beyond the exact outcome, the custom predictor is slower than AUGUSTUS, although not dramatically so. This problem could most probably be reduced by further optimizing the implementation, but since gene-predictions on different contigs are independent and can be run in parallel, distributing the workload onto multiple threads or simultaneously run jobs already renders the predictor feasibly useable in its current state.

More problematically, the custom predictor cannot incorporate ‘hints’ (information beyond the bare nucleotide-sequence, such as RNA-mapping), as AUGUSTUS can^[17]. Such hints generally markedly improve the prediction [internal communication]. Because the custom predictor closely follows the approach and theory of AUGUSTUS, it should reasonably be extendable to also incorporate hints in much the same way as AUGUSTUS. Alternatively (and with less programming-effort), the custom predictor can be used as a preprocessing step for AUGUSTUS, exactly like the simple preprocessors tried out here: Once the custom predictor has predicted which UGAs are sense-UGAs, they can be specifically replaced by UGG, and then AUGUSTUS can be trained and run on these modified data, further taking hints into account, and thereby hopefully improving on the foundation laid by the

preprocessor.

The inability to predict overlapping genes on opposing strands is a limit shared between AUGUSTUS and the custom GHMM here. It results from modelling both strands in the same GHMM that can then only be either on the forward or the reverse strand (by taking the respective states). Simply removing the backward-strand-submodel and running the prediction once on the forward and once on the backward strand is not a sensible solution, as the alternations in %GC between exons and non-coding sequences, and the codon-wise alternations of the base-frequencies found in exons are sequence-signals that stretch both strands. While the codon-structure does have a clear strandedness (complementary codons are not of equal frequency), that might hopefully (but not guaranteeably) be picked up by a predictor, the %GC-content is entirely strand-unspecific. Both may cause the predictor to make spurious predictions on one strand when there should only be a feature predicted on the opposing strand in that segment. Telling this apart from actual overlapping genes on complementary strands is then itself a nontrivial problem. Meanwhile, extending the mathematical framework to work on both strands in parallel should be possible, but equally is not straight-forward, and well beyond the scope of this thesis.

4.3 Outlook

Another unexplored limit of the predictor developed here is its generalizability to any species but *Loxodes magnus*. While other karyorelicts use the same genetic code^{[4],[19]}, it was not demonstrated here that the sequence-features that are exploited in the definition of the stop-region-state generally occur in other karyorelicts. However, similar depletion of ambiguous codons has been shown in one other karyorelict (*Parduczia sp.*) and the heterotrich *Condylostoma magnum*, and seems not to be mere coincidence, but biologically meaningful and (somewhat) general: If UGA (or other ambiguous codons) were to occur in the region where it is depleted, it would probably indeed be ambiguous even to the cell, leading to unfavourable random translation termination. There thus is a selective pressure to deplete UGA from the region where it is ambiguous, resulting in the altered codon-usage right upstream of the correct stop-UGA^[19]. It hence stands to be expected that the model can immediately generalize to other karyorelicts, especially other *Loxodes*-species (like *Loxodes striatus*), and other species using the same genetic code.

The reason for the observed depletion of UAA upstream of the proper stop remains unclear: This depletion might be due to the release-factor used by *Loxodes* having some remaining affinity for UAA, in which case a UAA in

the stop-region might lead to premature translation termination (probably with low efficiency, but still unfavourable) – which could then be detected experimentally. Alternatively, or in addition, since UAA is not as categorically depleted from the stop-region, its depletion may be a remnant of a previously used genetic code where UAA was still a stop-codon. However, this would not explain why there is no such depletion upstream of pseudostop-UAA. Instead, if the current release factor is entirely specific to UGA, the depletion of UAA might be a remnant of a time when the release factor still had a higher affinity of UAA (in addition to UGA), even though the overall code was the same.

For species like *C. magnum* using a different genetic code^[19], the model would need be adapted:

4.3.1 More and other ambiguous stop-codons

Karyorelicts are not the only ciliates with ambiguous genetic codes, *Condylostoma* in particular have an even more challenging code, with all three standard-stops being ambiguous. This would require additional stop-region-states, probably one for each stop-codon, that would ‘compete’ to end a given gene. Perhaps, a single stop-region would suffice, that then would not include the actual stop, but simply lead to three states for the three stop-codons respectively, and would itself only capture the stop-codon-depletion expected to occur upstream of the proper stop. Additionally, if there are multiple codons that can serve as stops, they may not be used equally often^[19], which is straight-forward to model by non-uniform transition probabilities in a GHMM.

Adapting the model like this seems to be feasible going by the depletion previously shown in *C. magnum*^[19], but a more detailed characterization of sense- vs stop-UGA, UAA and UAG in the particular species or genus at hand would be advisable.

4.3.2 Frameshifting

Another kind of deviation from the usual codon-by-codon genetic code is programmed ribosomal frameshifting (PRF), either by one nucleotide upstream (-1 PRF) or one downstream (+1 PRF), both of which have been found in diverse species, with -1PRF particularly noted in viruses, and the ciliate genus *Euplotes* featuring a number of +1PRF-reliant genes. Whereas -1PRF is mediated by well-conserved sequence-signals with a similar mechanism across species, +1PRF is less well-understood, and mediated by various mechanisms in different species. In *Euplotes*, there is a characteristic conserved sequence wherein a +1PRF occurs.^[21]

The GHMM presented here, or the GHMM presented by Mario Stanke^[17] could probably be adapted to predict genes in species with frequent programmed ribosomal frameshifts by introducing a state (or group of states) that similar to introns introduces a frameshift and emits a specific conserved sequence (called ‘slippery sequence’^[21]), potentially preceded and/or followed by other regions signalling the frameshift. Note that even in -1PRF, the GHMM could of course not emit a sequence of negative length, but would have to rely on modelling the surrounding sequence-features. Doing this simultaneously to gene-prediction should have the advantage of being able to use the rest of the gene’s features (introns, codon-usage in exons, start- and stop-region) to restrict where such a frameshift is plausible.

Appendix A

Further Tables and Details

A.1 Tables

A	-0.002	-0.022	0.16	-0.066	-0.099	0.234	-0.129	0.028	0.156	-0.03	-0.212	0.184	...	
	-0.206	-0.131	-0.068	-0.359	0.042	-0.437	-0.348	-0.068	-0.414	-0.555	0.009	-0.196	...	
	0.011	0.212	0.186	0.017	0.228	0.128	0.062	0.152	0.2	0.08	0.245	0.071	...	
	0.116	-0.338	-0.751	0.27	-0.393	-0.433	0.27	-0.33	-0.466	0.208	-0.214	-0.346	...	
	...	-0.022	-0.079	0.18	-0.142	-0.054	0.163	-0.15	0.077	0.044	1.727	-inf	-inf	...
	...	-0.187	-0.007	-0.403	-0.506	-0.206	-0.448	-0.592	-0.338	0.254	-inf	-inf	-inf	...
	...	-0.008	0.203	0.16	0.055	0.2	0.223	0.055	0.186	0.024	-inf	-inf	1.461	...
	...	0.166	-0.315	-0.416	0.362	-0.193	-0.525	0.403	-0.308	-0.353	-inf	2.361	-inf	...
	...	-0.452	0.197	0.333	0.051	0.017	0.312	-0.146	-0.091	0.224	0.036	0.114	0.238	...
	...	-0.226	-0.555	-0.103	-0.403	-0.007	-0.437	-0.359	0.09	-0.317	-0.37	0.098	-0.425	...
	...	0.343	0.083	-0.005	-0.025	0.137	0.14	-0.038	0.043	0.131	0.071	0.083	0.163	...
	...	0.03	-0.166	-0.615	0.203	-0.323	-0.681	0.44	-0.012	-0.508	0.042	-0.491	-0.552	...
	B	-0.383	0.29	0.042	-0.383	0.218	0.083	-0.355	-0.059	0.035	-0.208	-0.001	0.142	...
-0.193		0.308	-0.091	-0.193	0.332	0.079	0.483	0.404	-0.058	-0.074	0.108	0.205	...	
0.0		-0.281	0.098	0.024	-0.111	-0.06	-0.098	0.006	-0.124	-0.073	0.0	-0.21	...	
0.537		-0.297	-0.205	0.506	-0.517	-0.083	0.232	-0.284	0.194	0.418	-0.083	-0.025	...	
...		-0.127	0.049	0.035	-0.216	0.199	-0.081	-0.284	-0.008	0.531	1.123	-inf	-inf	...
...		0.004	0.064	0.15	-0.011	0.094	0.308	0.079	-0.091	0.191	-inf	-inf	-inf	...
...		-0.111	0.158	-0.054	-0.092	-0.048	-0.048	0.087	0.136	-0.585	-inf	-inf	1.496	...
...		0.341	-0.517	-0.071	0.418	-0.353	-0.037	0.165	-0.205	-0.27	-inf	3.562	-inf	...
...		-0.314	-0.411	-0.285	-0.326	-0.455	-0.078	0.032	-0.246	-0.138	0.05	-0.123	-0.078	...
...		-0.388	0.782	0.121	0.252	0.667	0.041	0.121	0.27	0.27	-0.134	0.321	0.021	...
...		-0.211	0.04	0.143	0.213	0.052	0.093	-0.057	0.223	0.149	0.046	0.127	0.223	...
...		1.542	0.443	0.516	0.264	0.684	-0.043	-0.096	-0.152	-0.332	-0.365	-0.398	-0.824	...
C		-0.858	-0.858	-0.226	-0.051	-0.425	-0.373	-0.322	-0.595	-0.373	-0.373	-0.425	-0.595	...
	0.901	0.901	-0.421	0.994	0.695	0.579	0.994	0.901	0.454	-1.006	-0.684	0.579	...	
	-0.486	0.236	-0.001	-0.721	0.099	0.099	-0.053	-0.416	0.146	-0.053	0.192	0.05	...	
	1.843	0.718	1.065	0.718	0.428	0.428	0.065	1.506	0.428	1.58	1.165	1.065	...	
	...	-0.48	-0.373	-0.322	0.177	-1.18	-0.373	0.177	-0.788	-0.18	1.123	-inf	-inf	...
	...	-0.006	-0.199	0.454	0.164	0.695	-0.199	0.316	-0.421	0.164	-inf	-inf	-inf	...
	...	0.192	-0.001	-0.001	-0.56	-0.108	0.321	-0.416	0.099	0.192	-inf	-inf	1.496	...
	...	0.959	1.258	0.718	0.58	1.843	0.428	0.065	1.718	-0.157	-inf	3.562	-inf	...
	...	-0.537	-0.373	-0.01	-0.273	-0.373	-0.273	-0.5	-0.351	-0.386	-0.179	0.103	0.021	...
	...	-0.006	1.242	0.454	-0.199	0.454	0.454	1.201	0.239	0.789	-0.327	-1.307	0.108	...
	...	0.514	-0.223	-0.108	0.514	0.362	0.146	0.183	0.354	0.24	0.24	0.164	0.113	...
	...	-0.157	0.258	-0.157	-1.742	-0.742	0.065	-1.12	-0.345	-0.648	0.16	-0.306	-1.043	...

Table A.1: Position weight matrices as constructed around **A** sense-UGA, **B** stop-UGA, **C** UGA in the 3'UTR. The entries '-inf' are such positions, where the respective base cannot occur, and thereby mark the position of the relevant UGA. Since the matrices are so broad, they are each broken into three 'lines'. Also, give the used prior (base-frequencies in CDS/UTR here)

Protein (group)	Proteins/Genes	n
Histone H2A	HTA1, HTA3, HTAY	3
Histone H2B.1	HTA2, HTB1, HTB2	3
Histone H3.4	HHT3, HHT4, unnamed	3
Histone H4	HHF2	1
30S ribosomal protein	S5, S15, S16, S17	4
40S ribosomal protein	S3a, S8-2 (twice), S12	4
50S ribosomal protein	L1P (twice), L3, L4, L7Ae, L13, L17, L20, L21, L24, L27, L36, L37e	13
60S ribosomal protein	L7 (twice), L17, L18 (twice), L24 (twice), L28, L29, L37, L39	11
		$\Sigma = 42$

Table A.2: Highly conserved proteins of *Tetrahymena*. Some of the proteins occur in two different locations in the genome, and are marked by ‘twice’ in parentheses. One of the Histone H3.4-genes is not named in the annotation, and thus given here as ‘unnamed’

A.2 Numerical example of the codon correction strategy

A numerical example of the codon correction strategy described in Methods will be given here, with the values based on the full training-dataset. Firstly, before correction, there are four relevant frequencies for each codon c :

- the empirical frequency f_c^{stop} of the codon in the stop-region (e.g. $f_{AAA}^{\text{stop}} = 6.109\%$)
- the empirical frequency f_c^{CDS} of the codon in CDS outside the stop-region (e.g. $f_{AAA}^{\text{CDS}} = 5.2157\%$)
- the probability p_c^{stop} of the codon in the stop-region according to the base-wise model (e.g. $p_{AAA}^{\text{stop}} = 3.6059\%$)
- the probability p_c^{CDS} of the codon in CDS outside the stop-region according to the base-wise model (e.g. $p_{AAA}^{\text{CDS}} = 4.6955\%$)

Based on the observed pattern of depletion, UGA and UAA are corrected, from $p_{UGA}^{\text{stop}} = 1.2684\%$ to $q_{UGA}^{\text{stop}} = f_{UGA}^{\text{stop}} = 0$, and from $p_{UAA}^{\text{stop}} = 2.8229\%$ to $q_{UAA}^{\text{stop}} = f_{UAA}^{\text{stop}} = 0.1880\%$ respectively.

From the above-listed four frequencies/probabilities, the two differences $\Delta_c^{\text{emp}} = f_c^{\text{stop}} - f_c^{\text{CDS}}$ (e.g. $\Delta_{AAA}^{\text{emp}} = 0.8933\%$) and $\Delta_c^{\text{simple}} = p_c^{\text{stop}} - p_c^{\text{CDS}}$ (e.g. $\Delta_{AAA}^{\text{simple}} = -1.0896\%$) arise, each denoting the change in codon usage between regular CDS and the stop-region (empirically and under the simple model respectively). This change is an important signal to identify the stop-UGA, so it should be faithfully captured by the GHMM.

Under the base-wise model, the example-codon AAA used so far e.g. is wrongly depleted in stop-regions, even though it empirically is slightly

enriched. Indeed, of all codons except UGA and UAA (which are chosen a priori to be corrected), AAA in this example has the highest difference $\Delta\Delta_c = |\Delta_c^{\text{emp}} - \Delta_c^{\text{simple}}|$:

For AAA, this value here is $\Delta\Delta_{AAA} = 1.9829\%$. The codons with the next-highest differences are e.g. $\Delta\Delta_{AGA} = 1.6777\%$ and $\Delta\Delta_{CAT} = 1.2132\%$.

Thereby, AAA is chosen to be c^* , and has its q_{AAA}^{stop} set to $= 6.109\%$. At this point, three corrections have been made (UGA, UAA and AAA), resulting in the summed up correction-probabilities, as compared to the summed up uncorrected probabilities being:

$$q_{UGA}^{\text{stop}} + q_{UAA}^{\text{stop}} + q_{AAA}^{\text{stop}} = 6.2970\% \text{ vs. } p_{UGA}^{\text{stop}} + p_{UAA}^{\text{stop}} + p_{AAA}^{\text{stop}} = 7.6972\%$$

I.e. the *remainder* δ is in this example $\delta = 1.4002\%$. To have the corrected distribution indeed be a distribution, this remainder needs to be quenched somehow. If one were to e.g. find a codon c^+ with exactly $f_{c^+}^{\text{stop}} = \delta + p_{c^+}^{\text{stop}}$ (e.g. $f_{c^+}^{\text{stop}} = 2.9368\%$ and $p_{c^+}^{\text{stop}} = 2.9368\% - 1.4002\% = 1.5366\%$), then one could add this c^+ to the correction-set R , and get:

$$\sum_{c \in R} q_c^{\text{stop}} = 6.2970\% + \overbrace{2.9368\%}^{\delta + p_{c^+}^{\text{stop}}} = 9.2338\% = 7.6972\% + 1.5366\% = \sum_{c \in R} p_c^{\text{stop}}$$

Since this perfect codon may not exist, the codon that comes closest (i.e. has minimal $|f_c^{\text{stop}} - p_c^{\text{stop}} - \delta|$) is chosen instead: In the example, this is GCT with $f_{GCT}^{\text{stop}} = 2.9135\%$, $p_{GCT}^{\text{stop}} = 1.5366\% \Rightarrow f_{GCT}^{\text{stop}} - p_{GCT}^{\text{stop}} = 1.3769\%$.

The next-best codon here is AAG with $f_{AAG}^{\text{stop}} = 3.2895\%$, $p_{AAG}^{\text{stop}} = 1.8348\% \Rightarrow f_{AAG}^{\text{stop}} - p_{AAG}^{\text{stop}} = 1.4547\%$.

Then, GCT is corrected to $q_{GCT}^{\text{stop}} = 2.9368\%$ (which is slightly different from its empirical frequency), and the distribution is thus normalized.

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